

DELVING INTO THE CASES OF HIGH SCHOOL READING COORDINATORS IN SCAFFOLDING NON-READER STUDENTS: A CASE STUDY

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 30

Issue 6

Pages: 1071-1114

Document ID: 2025PEMJ2896

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14628443

Manuscript Accepted: 12-17-2024

Delving into the Cases of High School Reading Coordinators in Scaffolding Non-Reader Students: A Case Study

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Abstract

This research investigates the methodologies and approaches utilized by high school reading coordinators in scaffolding non-reader students. With a growing recognition of the importance of literacy skills for academic success, particularly at the high school level, this study aims to delve into the specific strategies employed by reading coordinators to support students who struggle with reading proficiency. This study utilized a qualitative method using the case study approach in its conduct. The participants were five reading coordinators in five secondary schools in the Municipality of Kapalong. The research explores various scaffolding techniques, instructional interventions, and differentiated approaches adopted by reading coordinators to facilitate the development of reading skills among non-reader students. Furthermore, the study will examine the challenges faced by reading coordinators and how they cope with them, as well as the insights of reading coordinators in scaffolding non-reader students. Ultimately, the findings of this research aim to contribute to a deeper understanding of effective strategies for supporting non-reader students in high school settings, with implications for policy, practice, and future research in the field of literacy education.

Keywords: *non-readers, reading coordinators, scaffolding, qualitative research, Philippines*

Introduction

Studying the cases of high school reading coordinators who scaffolded non-reader students allows us to examine the different strategies and techniques that these coordinators used to work with non-readers. It is vital to scaffold non-reader pupils because it provides individualized, step-by-step guidance that helps them overcome difficulties, gain confidence, and eventually succeed academically. Furthermore, non-reader students frequently struggle with basic literacy abilities, which can cause serious gaps in their academic performance and self-esteem and make it difficult for them to succeed in school and engage with the lessons being taught. There are students who are non-readers and the perceived causes, origins and attendant variables of the students' reading level were non-mastery of the elements of reading, presence of learners-at-risk, and no culture of reading. The perceived causes of non-mastery of the elements of reading are: no phonological awareness, non-mastery of alphabet knowledge, non-mastery of phonics, poor word recognition and vocabulary, poor fluency skills, and lack of comprehension (Tomas et al., 2021).

In Virginia, one study found that 3early reading abilities were at a 20-year low this semester according to one study, which the researchers called "alarming." While children from all demographic groups have been impacted, Black and Hispanic children, as well as those from low-income families, those with disabilities, and those who do not speak English fluently, were left behind the most. Results from national and international tests in 2019 revealed a static or declining reading proficiency in the United States along with growing differences between high and low achievers. While there are many different reasons, a lack of phonics and phonemic awareness-trained teachers is one of the main ones, according to several experts (Goldstein, 2022).

Moreover, in Baguio City, Philippines, public schools are grappling with an increasing number of non-readers and frustration-level readers. This issue was highlighted in a February report by the Philippine Institute for Development Studies, which urged the Department of Education (DepEd) to stop the practice of promoting non-readers from elementary to high school. According to the report, the presence of non-readers in high schools indicates that current reading programs and the K-12 curriculum are not meeting their goals. Consequently, there is a growing call for educational reforms to address these literacy challenges and improve the overall quality of education (Dumlao, 2019).

Delving into the cases of high school reading coordinators who specialize in scaffolding non-reader students holds significant social importance. It is crucial to understand effective strategies for fostering literacy skills. By examining these cases, educators can gain insights into tailored instructional methods, resource allocation, and support structures that contribute to the successful development of reading abilities in students facing challenges in literacy. It can help address the pressing issue of illiteracy and low reading proficiency, which have long-term consequences for individuals and society. Also, this research can shed light on effective strategies and interventions that can be shared and implemented across schools to improve literacy rates.

In conducting this literature review, several relevant studies were identified, including Tomas's (2021) "The Perceived Challenges in Reading of Learners: Basis for School Reading Programs" which only examined the challenges of the learners while reading. Conversely, the study entitled "L.O.V.E. Reading Program: Improving Oral Reading Fluency among Struggling Readers of BeNHS" by Sampang (2022) focused only on the reading fluency among struggling readers and not on scaffolding non-reader students. This particular study differs from others by placing greater emphasis on the cases of high school reading coordinators scaffolding non-reader students, specifically in Kapalong, Davao del Norte. These premises guided the proposal for this particular study.

The findings will be shared through a presentation to the DepEd Division of Davao del Norte, highlighting actionable insights that can inform reading programs and support practices for non-readers. Next, a comprehensive report detailing the cases, strategies, and outcomes will be distributed to school administrators, teachers, and reading coordinators across various schools. Furthermore, the researcher will seek opportunities to present at education-focused conferences and seminars, enabling a broader exchange of knowledge and ideas.

Research Questions

The primary purpose of this study was to delve into the cases of reading coordinators in scaffolding non-readers, to go more deeply understanding and to highlight the participants' points of view, opinions, ideas, and feelings. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What techniques and strategies are used by the reading coordinator when dealing with students who are non-readers?
2. What are the lived experiences of the reading coordinators with non-reader students?
3. What coping mechanisms do they employ to deal with the issue of scaffolding non-readers?
4. What are the insights of reading coordinators on scaffolding students who are non-readers?

Methodology

Research Design

Deeper understanding and exploration of real-world issues are provided by qualitative research. Qualitative research collects the views, behaviors, and experiences of people. It is possible to quantify qualitative data, but at its core, qualitative data seeks themes and patterns that can be challenging to measure. It answers the how's and whys instead of how many or how much. This review introduces the readers to some basic concepts, definitions, terminology, and application of qualitative research (Tenny, 2022).

The study will use a qualitative research design to investigate how high school reading coordinators scaffold non-reader students. It will use methods such as interviews to gather information about the methods and techniques that of these coordinators employ, their experiences dealing with non-readers, and how they handle the difficulties they experience.

Specifically, a case study is an empirical inquiry that examines a phenomena within the context of actual events. Due to the fact that case study research involves a comprehensive analysis of a phenomenon, a variety of data collection methodologies are utilized. It's crucial to keep in mind that a case study is a research approach or methodology that looks at a social unit rather than a data collection method (Yin, 2009).

By focusing on individual cases, researcher can explore the unique strategies, challenges, and outcomes experienced by reading coordinators in their efforts to support non-reader students. In delving into the cases of high school reading coordinators who support non-reader students, this approach becomes particularly valuable. This case study aims to uncover how these professionals scaffold the reading development of students who struggle with reading. This approach allows for a comprehensive understanding of the practices and factors that contribute to successful reading intervention for non-reader students.

Participants

The main participants in the study were reading coordinators from five secondary schools in the Municipality of Kapalong, Davao del Norte, namely: Kapalong National High School, Luna National High School, Sampao Integrated School, Semong National High School, and Baltazar Nicor Valenzuela National High School. According to the criteria of the study, five (5) participants came from the five secondary schools in Kapalong. The selection of participants is justified because the intended participants of the study are reading coordinators. Thus, they are the only ones capable of providing authentic accounts about the research topic. The researcher conducted in-depth interviews with all five (5) individuals, doing one-on-one or online interviews with each participant.

This number was chosen in accordance with Creswell's (2013) recommendation that there should be between three (3) and fifteen (15) participants in a case study. By incorporating this group of participants in a qualitative research study, data saturation was attained in the data gathering procedure.

The criteria specified by the researcher were appropriate for the study. The following criteria were used to choose the participants. They must be a reading coordinator of a secondary school located in the Municipality of Kapalong, Davao del Norte. Also, the reading coordinator should have significant experience working with non-reader students, preferably with a proven track record of success in improving their reading skills. This includes both the number of years in the role and the variety of contexts in which they have worked.

Procedure

The following steps were employed in gathering the data:

First, the researcher sought permission to conduct the study as well as approval from the IATF. Through the purposive sampling technique, five (5) participants were identified. They are requested to read and understand the consent form and agreement form before they sign to make sure that their participation in my research study is voluntary and not coerced. These forms contain a condition

specifying that the informant's participation is voluntary and that they are willing to impart their knowledge, which is essentially needed for the success of this study.

Secondly, the participants in the study had been given orientation about the study. The orientation started with an introductory phase, in which the researcher outlined the purpose of the interview, its length, and confidentiality. The researcher also took into account that the informants received benefits from cooperating with us. It requires providing treatment to all the participants in an in-depth interview. Further, the informants and the researcher should both benefit from the research. The informants were given the chance to unload their perceptions based on the experiences that they had, which would be substantial components in making this study successful; lastly, the informants became my research partners who help the researcher disseminate the findings of the research for academic purposes.

Also, during the interview, the data from the responses of the informants/participants were recorded through smartphones. The recorded data had been transcribed by the researcher before being translated from raw language to Standard English Language. After the translation of the data, the researcher would extract the emerging themes following the principles of thematic analysis. Lastly, the extracted themes are handed over to the data analyst, whose expertise is aligned with the concept of language research, for verification and approval (Creswell, 2013).

Data Analysis

After gathering all necessary relevant detail data, the organization of data was processed, and only then was it time to examine it. The data are systematically organized using qualitative analysis, which requires a thorough examination of the raw data in the context of its logical category. The data is operated, arranged, and broken down into management, analysis, and discussion of what was important and what should also be learned.

Researcher also participate in content analysis, which refers to research techniques for examining documents and communication artifacts, such as texts in a variety of formats. This made it easier to interpret the material in specific articles, papers, interviews, and other sources. Additionally, it assists the researcher in retaining the necessary information for usage (Pashakhanlou, 2017).

In context, the researcher also took part in content analysis in researching how high school reading coordinators help non-reader students. This involves studying documents and communication materials like texts in various formats. It made it easier to understand specific articles, papers, interviews, and other sources about the coordinators' work. Additionally, it helped the researcher keep important information for later use.

Additionally, the social sciences—including history, managerial and leadership studies, organizational theory, business studies, and political sciences—often make extensive use of context analysis. It is helpful for locating trends and subjects in contexts of unstructured data. Contextual analysis in some ways aids in bringing order out of disarray. Contextual analysis' primary goal is to determine when and how a social phenomenon is shaped by its context, and vice versa (Willems, 2021).

In context, studying high school reading coordinators who help non-reader students, context analysis is very useful. It helps identify patterns and key issues in the complex data from their experiences and strategies. This method organizes diverse information, making it easier to understand how these coordinators work. The goal is to see how the coordinators' actions are shaped

Ethical Considerations

Research ethics deals with the interaction between study subjects and researchers. This suggests that the welfare of research subjects should always come first when studying them. The researcher conducted the research in accordance with the following ethical standards: respect for individuals, beneficence, justice, consent, and secrecy. Additionally, the participants' privacy was protected, their full consent was sought, and respect for their dignity was ensured in order to ensure the participants' safety (Mack et al., 2005).

In context, the participant's wellbeing was always given priority in the connection between the researcher and the subjects, which was conducted in strict accordance with research ethics. The study was carried out in accordance with ethical guidelines that included secrecy, beneficence, justice, consent, and respect for the worth of individuals. To guarantee their safety during the study, participants' privacy was maintained, their complete consent was acquired, and their dignity was upheld. This approach guaranteed the integrity and dependability of the research findings in addition to providing protection for the participants.

Respect for persons is the principle that requires a commitment to ensuring the autonomy of research participants, and, where autonomy may be diminished, to protect people from exploitation of their vulnerability. The dignity of all research participants must be respected. Adherence to this principle ensures that people are not used simply as a means to achieve research objectives (Mack et al., 2005).

In context, to ensure that a person's rights were protected, qualitative research needs to adhere to some criteria in order to maintain its ethicality. In regards to this inquiry, permission is obtained from the selected participants before recording the full conversation and all the responses of the participants because consent should be obtained. Respecting the dignity of all research participants is a fundamental ethical principle in research and educational settings. This principle entails recognizing and upholding the intrinsic worth and rights of individuals involved in research.

Consent was formalized to protect people's right to choose whether or not to engage in research by fostering research interactions built

on "trust and integrity." The fact that a person's decision is voluntary and founded on accurate knowledge about the implications of participating in the research is a crucial need for the validity of consent (Klykken, 2021).

In context, the participants urged to make informed choices and to participate voluntarily in order to adhere to ethical standards for conducting research. Additionally, the research informs the participants that they have the right to ask questions during the interview, rights to refuse to answer sensitive questions, and rights to leave the interview without any explanation. If the participants leave in the middle of the interview, the researcher would respect the participants' decision to not finish the interview. Nevertheless, the interview went well. The researcher made sure that every participant is enthusiastic and driven to contribute to the success of this study. Also, when the subject is being interviewed, the researcher requested consent to record the entire exchange in order to get a complete picture of their experiences. Also, the researcher informs the participants that they have the rights to be informed of the study result.

Benevolence, a fundamental ethical principle in research, places a strong emphasis on the researcher's obligation to protect the safety and well-being of study participants. This principle is often encapsulated by the phrase "do no harm," emphasizing the need to avoid causing any unnecessary risks or negative consequences for those involved in the research. Furthermore, the idea of maximizing benefits while minimizing harm is also crucial to benevolence (Farrugia, 2019).

The community and participants would benefit from this study because the result of this study may become the basis for improving the curriculum guide in scaffolding non-reader students and it can lead into the formulation of effective teaching techniques and strategies that assist the student in reading and improve the quality of education in the community. The researcher locates a secure location where the participants and researcher can conduct a face-to-face interview in order to ensure the safety of all participants. Participants in the interview process are afforded the opportunity to share their personal stories in a supportive and secure environment, ensuring they feel comfortable without any fear of rejection or criticism from others. The information was kept private and secure after the interview to avoid psychological risks such as shame, embarrassment, and other negative outcomes. The research ensures that the risk of COVID-19 transmission between the interviewer and participants was avoided by following safety protocols during the interview.

Justice requires a commitment to ensure a fair distribution of the risks and benefits resulting from research. Those who took on the burdens of research participation should share in the benefits of the knowledge gained. Or, to put it another way, the people who are expected to benefit from the knowledge should be the ones who are asked to participate (Department of Health, Education, and Welfare, & National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research, 2014).

In context, this study utilizes in-depth interview to be manifested through the fair analysis of each material. The researcher made sure that the method of analysis is free from personal bias. The data were treated in accordance with the research questions and theoretical frameworks of this inquiry and not from my own capacity. This ensures that justice was served and fairness was prevailing in this qualitative inquiry.

Confidentiality respects the privacy of human subjects when gathering, analyzing, and reporting data, confidentiality is a moral practice. Separating or altering any personally identifying data provided by participants from the data is referred to as confidentiality. The participant's identity was maintained through the use of codes. Protecting the data gathered and ensuring that it is only used for the research's stated purposes is the researcher's first priority (Coffelt, 2017). Also, in this study, confidentiality was maintained through the use of password-protected folders and data storage. This also corroborates with the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

In order to protect the participants' privacy, the researcher would conceal the participants' identities, such as their names and addresses. The names of the participants were replaced by pseudonyms by the researcher. Participants' names and other identifying information may be kept in separate, secure files. Research data were stored and destroyed three years after the accomplishment of the study.

Results and Discussion

Participants

The participants of this study were selected reading coordinators in five secondary schools in the Municipality of Kapalong, Davao del Norte. The participants will focus only on the scaffolding techniques they employ for scaffolding non-reader students. They all have their own pseudonyms, which they use to protect their identities. The participants were all public reading coordinators. By doing so, the researcher placed her trust in them, believing that they could contribute to the study's objectives. Finally, they show remarkable scaffolding techniques for helping non-reader students.

The interviews took place inside the campus, and the researcher spoke with them about where they preferred to be interviewed. The participants were given an overview of the study. The researcher got where he wanted to go, and both the interviewer and the interviewee were pleased with the end result, resulting in a seamless flow and open communication whenever extra or probing questions were required. Participants had the option of refusing to answer any question that they deemed unprofitable or against their choices. The data collected during the interviews was kept in strict discretion to guarantee confidentiality, and only the researcher and informants had access to any information that was expressed but not included due to the study's nature.

To comply with the data collection method, the researcher utilized her cellphone as a substitute for the required tape recorder, recording the participants' responses to ensure accuracy and preserve the integrity of the data. The researcher also inquired if she could capture

videos or photos during the interviews to enhance the documentation. However, all of the respondents politely declined the request, expressing a preference for the researcher to solely record the entire conversation instead. All participants complied with the researcher's requests, except for one, that their identities remain anonymous throughout the course of the research study (Boyce & Neale, 2006).

Table 1. *Participants of the Study*

<i>Pseudonyms</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Code</i>
Smart	32	Female	IDI-01
Confident	30	Female	IDI-02
Simple	35	Female	IDI-03
Approachable	31	Female	IDI-04
Enthusiastic	30	Female	IDI-05

Categorization of the Data

The voice-recorded discussions were transcribed, translated, and analyzed once the in-depth interviews were completed. The researcher highlighted the use of data coding and thematic analysis to construct themes in this study. In the process of coding, the researcher will arrange the resources into pieces of text before giving meaning to the information. The coding technique was utilized to provide a description of the setting of people as well as the categories of themes to be analyzed. These topics were used to help form a broad description of the phenomena under investigation.

The voice-recorded discussions were transcribed, translated, and analyzed once the in-depth interviews were completed. The researcher initiated the analysis with the process of coding. Coding is the technique of arranging the resources into pieces of text segments before giving meaning to information. The coding technique was utilized to provide a description of the setting of people as well as the categories of themes to be analyzed. These topics were used to help form a broad description of the phenomena under investigation.

For the data to be categorized, the themes were presented by the research question and referred to as major themes. The themes that had emerged from the study were discussed and elaborated thoroughly to provide a vivid description. Then came the drawing of the conclusion and verification of points in the study, in which the preliminary ideas and procedures about the findings were developed (Miles & Huberman, 1994).

The researcher took notice of the constructs of credibility, dependability, transferability, and confirmability in order to add trustworthiness to our study. In addition to the triangulation approach, member verification was done to address credibility. This was achieved by giving participants a copy of the interview transcript so they could provide comments and attest to its accuracy. So far, none of the participants have raised any objections to the transcript or provided any input to the contrary. They all signed the participant's verification form to confirm their affirmative response. The study's triangulation was made possible by the fact that it included more than two sources, specifically readings from related literature and participants (Cresswell & Miller, 2003).

The researcher supplied an audit trail that was referred to to ensure dependability and confirmability. It was created to allow the research review panel to confirm results, assumptions, and conjectures (Carcary, 2009). In terms of transferability, the researcher stated from the beginning that the results could not be generalized because these views were based only on the participants' own experiences in the indicated localities. Nonetheless, the researcher agreed that when the credibility, confirmability, and dependability of a qualitative case study are assured, then transferability is addressed as well (Gempes et al., 2009).

Case 1- Smart

Smart, not her real name, is a female reading coordinator at one secondary school in the Municipality of Kapalong. She is 32 years old.

When helping non-reader students, Smart focuses on creating a positive and supportive classroom environment. She uses interactive learning activities to engage students, revisits basic reading skills to build a strong foundation, and incorporates guided individual reading sessions. Additionally, she employs peer tutoring, allowing students to help each other, which further enhances students learning.

Smart shared the difficulties she experiences in scaffolding non-reader students. She deals with students who feel embarrassed about not being able to read, which affects their willingness to participate. Additionally, she encounters students with short attention spans and low retention. Nevertheless, to manage the challenges she took into account each student's background and personal situation, she also uses a reward system to encourage and motivate students, making learning more engaging. Smart believes that focusing on building a strong reading foundation at the elementary level is crucial for future success. She emphasizes that, as a reading coordinator, having a lot of patience is essential to effectively supporting and guiding students through their learning process. Additionally, she finds a deep sense of fulfillment in teaching, which helps her stay motivated and committed to her role.

Research Question No. 1: What techniques and strategies are used by the reading coordinator when dealing with students who are non-readers?

To answer this research question, an in-depth interview was conducted. Hence, several sub-questions were asked about the techniques and strategies used by the reading coordinators when dealing with non-readers. From her answers, the researcher identified the

following main themes: creating a positive class climate, employing interactive learning activities, going back to the basics, utilizing a guided individual reading strategy, and employing peer tutoring.

Creating a Positive Class Climate

In scaffolding non-reader students, reading coordinators create a welcoming, inclusive environment that encourages students to feel a sense of belonging. By building confidence and providing tailored support, reading coordinators ensure that non-readers do not feel marginalized or behind. This positive, supportive atmosphere motivates non-readers to engage with learning, as they are empowered to believe in their abilities. The reading coordinator's role is crucial in ensuring non-readers feel capable, fostering their growth and development in reading.

Smart (pseudonym) discussed her methods for supporting students who struggle with reading, emphasizing the importance of maintaining a positive learning environment. One of her key strategies is to avoid labeling her students as "non-readers," a choice she makes to build their confidence and prevent them from feeling inferior. Smart aims to foster a sense of belonging and motivation among her students. She said:

"We will not be calling them non-readers or struggling readers, we just explain that they are part of a reading program, and we choose them because we see potential in them. I know they already have an idea why they are part of the reading program, but as a teacher, you also need to establish confidence in your students so they will not feel behind." (IDI-01)

(We will not refer to them as non-readers or struggling readers; instead, we will explain that they are part of a reading program because we see potential in them. I know they already have an idea of why they are in the reading program, but as a teacher, it is important to build their confidence so they do not feel left behind.)

Employing Interactive Learning Activities

Reading coordinators recognize that scaffolding non-reader students with interactive learning activities is an effective strategy for fostering interest in reading and enhancing literacy skills. Activities like games, group discussions, and collaborative tasks not only make learning more enjoyable but also create a dynamic and engaging classroom. By emphasizing participation and teamwork, these activities build non-readers' confidence, providing them with a supportive environment where they can actively engage with the material and feel motivated to improve their reading skills.

Smart (pseudonym) shares that in scaffolding non-reader students, she employs interactive learning activities. She said that for students to be interested in what they are learning and to enjoy themselves, interactive learning activities are essential. Activities allow students to stay engaged in their learning. She discussed how crucial it is to use interactive learning activities to keep kids interested and having fun while learning. She Shared:

"We also incorporate mga game activities or play not use literal activities dapat hands on gyud na sila di lang na sila basa ug basa they also need to manipulate objects and paper kay ug mu ingon kag basaha ni tudlo tudlo lang ka they will not appreciate the learning process." (IDI-01)

(We also incorporate games, activities, or play, not just literal activities. We need to be hands-on, not just always reading they also need to manipulate objects and paper, because when you tell them to read something just by pointing it, they will not appreciate the learning process.)

Going Back to the Basics

Going back to the basics involves focusing on the foundational skills necessary for reading, starting with recognizing letters and their corresponding sounds. It helps students understand how letters combine to form words, which is essential for decoding text. By building this strong base, students gain the confidence and skills needed to progress to more complex reading tasks and ultimately become proficient readers.

At this point, Smart (pseudonym) elaborated on her approach to scaffolding non-reader students, emphasizing the importance of mastering foundational skills before tackling more complex concepts. She begins by ensuring her students can recognize and understand the letters and sounds of the alphabet, which she believes is crucial for building their confidence and competence in reading. She stated that:

"You must use unified or simplified instruction, you would start from the basic you would start recognizing letters, sounds mas maayu man jud nang makabalo silag basa kaysa tudluan silag lesson kay di man gihapun na musulod sa utok." (IDI-01)

(Use easy activities, the basics, before proceeding to more complicated ones. You must use unified or simplified instructions. You would start from the basics; you would start recognizing letters and sounds. It is better that they know how to read than teach them lessons because they still cannot comprehend the lessons if they do not know how to read.)

Utilizing Guided Individual Reading Strategy

Utilizing the Guided Individual Reading Strategy in scaffolding non-readers allows for personalized attention and tailored instruction,

which can enhance learning outcomes. There are students who want to learn with the teacher and when directed by a single person, students receive immediate feedback and support, helping them navigate challenges and build their reading skills more effectively.

Smart (pseudonym) scaffolds her non-reader pupils using the guided individual reading strategy, emphasizing personalized attention to address their unique needs. She believes this technique works well because some students feel more comfortable and focused when learning one-on-one with the teacher. By tailoring the instruction, she fosters faster progress and builds their confidence in reading. She stated that:

“Not all student wants to learn with other students, naa juy mga bata nga mas gusto nila nga ikaw lang teacher and student lang naay mga in ana, isa na siya sa mga struggle of course dili jud nimu na siya ma force no kay basig mawala pud iyahang interest so dili lang jud nimu siya e mingle sa ubang bata,” (IDI-01)

(Not all students want to learn with other students; there are students who want to learn with only the teacher and student. That is one of the struggles because you cannot force the student because it might affect their interest in learning, that is why you just do not make that student learn with other students.)

Employing Peer Tutoring

Employing peer tutoring in scaffolding non-reader students allows them to collaborate with their peers. Through this collaboration, students can share strategies, practice reading together, and learn from one another's strengths and weaknesses. This approach not only enhances their reading skills but also builds social connections and boosts their confidence as they take role in each other's learning process.

Moreover, Smart (pseudonym) was asked what approach or strategy she found most effective in supporting other non-reading students to help them develop their literary skills. She said that as a reading coordinator, you also need to collaborate with other readers or independent readers in order to allow your learners to share and learn together. She stated that:

“You need to collaborate with other reader that is same level, they would share would learn together mugamit ko ug peer tutoring, I ask independent readers to teach them.” (IDI-01)

(You need to collaborate with other readers of the same level, they would share and learn together. Use peer tutoring, I ask independent readers to teach them.)

Research Question No. 2: What are the lived experiences of the reading coordinators with non-reader students?

In the second question, the participant was asked about her lived experiences as a reading coordinator with non-reader students. Her responses undergo thematic analysis, and the researcher identified the following emerging themes that were formed: encounter students who felt ashamed and dealt with short attention span and low retention.

Encounter Students Who Felt Ashamed

In scaffolding non-reader students, it's crucial to address the emotional barriers that hinder their progress, such as feelings of shame and embarrassment. Reading coordinators can counter these emotional challenges by fostering a supportive and non-judgmental environment where students feel safe to participate and take risks in their learning. By building their confidence and addressing these emotional barriers, coordinators help students overcome the shame they may feel and motivate them to engage in the learning process.

During the interview, Smart (pseudonym) shared that the most common barriers that non-reader encounter is struggling with embarrassment. In her role as a reading coordinator, she works with students who struggle with the shame and embarrassment of being non-readers. This barrier makes them feel ashamed, which is why their reading center is located at the end of the school campus. She stated that:

“Isa sa akong nakita is ma ulaw sila, as you can see our reading center is located sa tumoy kilid kaayu.” (IDI-01)

(One of the things I noticed is that they are ashamed, as you can see, our reading center is at the end of the school.)

Dealt with Short Attention Span and Low Retention

Reading coordinators often struggle with short attention spans and low retention of non-reader students, which can hinder their ability to absorb reading material effectively. This challenge may stem from early experiences in which they did not receive adequate support in literacy activities, leading to difficulties in maintaining focus.

At this point, Smart (pseudonym) shares that the reason there are students who are not readers is because they struggle with memory retention and attention deficit problems. When scaffolding non-reader students, the reading coordinator stated that they were dealing with pupils who had poor recall and a short attention span, and it was giving them a hard time teaching them how to read. She stated that

“They have also short attention span kasi sa ilahang early age wala kaau na establish ang discipline, wala kaayu because lack of

assistance.” (IDI-01)

(Non-readers also have a short attention span because, at their early age, discipline is not well established because lack of assistance.)

Research Question No. 3: What coping mechanisms do they employ to deal with the issue of scaffolding non-readers?

In the third question, the participant was asked what coping mechanisms she employs to deal with the issues of scaffolding non-reader students. This includes the strategy, techniques, and steps that she employs in facing the challenges she encounters. In the response of the participant, the researcher identified the following themes in the coding process, which are: considering the student's background and situations; and using a reward system.

Considering the student's background and situation

Reading coordinators emphasize understanding each student's background and circumstances to address their reading challenges effectively. This personalized approach allows them to identify factors such as home environment, prior learning gaps, and emotional barriers, enabling the use of tailored strategies that support individual growth, foster confidence, and enhance literacy development.

During the interview, Smart (pseudonym) shares that she used to overcome all the challenges as a reading coordinator by considering the student's background and situations because it is a factor in understanding why the student doesn't know how to read and what makes them have difficulty learning to read. Teachers can better fulfill the needs of the students based on their awareness of the students' backgrounds. She said that:

“When I handle non-reader students, I understand the different situations of students and how they become like that, so I need to adjust my strategy.” (IDI-01)

(When I work with non-reader students, I take into account their various circumstances and the reasons behind their struggles, so can adjust my teaching strategies accordingly.)

Using Reward System

In scaffolding non-reader students, reading coordinators use rewards such as stickers, praise, or small prizes as an essential strategy to encourage participation and motivate learners. These incentives provide positive reinforcement, helping students feel recognized for their efforts and achievements, no matter how small. This approach fosters a sense of accomplishment and helps sustain motivation, driving continued improvement in their reading skills.

At this point, Smart (pseudonym) shared that the reward system is what she uses to cope with the challenges in scaffolding non-reader. She stated that in her class, she gives her students a reward if they accomplish something, and in that way, the students will be motivated to learn in her class because she believes that students in secondary school are still kids. She said that:

“The reward system “ug makabasa ka tagaan takag ballpen, mabasa gani nimu ni tanan dire kaning 50 words unya kung mamali kag isa kuhaan natu imong candy” mostly sa struggling readers is grade 7 and grade 7 is still young still kids.” (IDI-01)

(The reward system, "If you can read, I will give you ballpen, read all the 50 words here, and if you have one mistake, I will take one of the candy." Most struggling readers are in grade 7, and grade 7 is still young still kids.)

Research Question No. 4: What are the insights of reading coordinators on scaffolding students who are non-readers?

To answer the last research question, an in-depth interview was conducted with the participant, respectively. Hence, several sub-questions were asked to provide her thoughts as a reading coordinator on scaffolding students who are non-readers. From her answers, the researcher identified the following main themes: give emphasis on the foundation, demonstrate unwavering patience, and gain a sense of fulfillment.

Give Emphasis on the Foundation

In scaffolding non-reader students, emphasizing foundational reading skills is essential, as many non-readers lack the basic literacy knowledge they should have developed in earlier grades. Without this solid foundation, students struggle to understand more advanced reading concepts, hindering their overall progress. Reading coordinators address this gap by focusing on rebuilding these core skills, ensuring that students have the necessary tools to progress in their literacy journey. By prioritizing these fundamentals, coordinators help students make meaningful progress.

During the interview, Smart (pseudonym) share that some students remain non-readers because the foundational reading skills they were supposed to acquire at an early age were not adequately nurtured. Smart firmly believes that a strong reading foundation must be established at the elementary level to ensure students are prepared for the more complex literacy demands of secondary education. She stated that:

“They are not actually can read because the foundation that they have in early age is not actually funded dili siya establish. From elementary dapat mao jud na siyay foundation sa reading, lisod na man gud sa highschool, why not DepEd would focus on numeracy

and literacy in elementary and not let them proceed to the next level if they do not master the skills that they need to master in that particular level.” (IDI-01)

(They are not actually able to read because the foundation that they have at an early age is not actually funded, it is not established. From elementary school on, it must be the foundation for reading because it is hard when they are already in high school. Why not DepEd focus on numeracy and literacy in elementary and not let them proceed to the next level if they do not master the skills that they need to master in that particular level.)

Demonstrate Unwavering Patience

Scaffolding non-reader students requires a reading coordinator to demonstrate unwavering patience, recognizing that these students often need more time and individualized support to master foundational reading skills. Since each student progresses at their own pace, patient guidance is essential in fostering a safe, supportive environment where students feel comfortable practicing without fear of judgment.

At this point, Smart (pseudonym) emphasized that scaffolding non-reader students requires a reading coordinator to demonstrate unwavering patience. Smart explained and highlighted that understanding and addressing these deeper issues is crucial, as the problem often stems from the student’s struggles rather than the content itself. She stated that:

“Be patient, mag baon ka talaga nang maraming pasensiya kay ang problema man gyud nimu ana no is the bata gyud.” (IDI-01)

(We need to be patient. Be very patient because your problem is the child itself.)

Gain a Sense of Fulfilment

Reading coordinators gain a deep sense of fulfillment from witnessing the progress of non-readers, knowing their efforts have made a real impact. Even when a student learns to read just two or three words, it represents a significant achievement and shows the value of their hard work and dedication. These small yet meaningful successes highlight the positive difference they make, bringing both encouragement and motivation to continue their work with non-readers.

Smart (pseudonym) shared that after successfully teaching non-reader students, she experiences a deep sense of fulfillment. She recounted a particular instance where she was able to make a significant impact on a non-reader, transforming their reading abilities and confidence. For her, the greatest joy comes from witnessing the progress of her students She stated that:

“I am very happy, last time katung student nako last year kay dre mi nag klase na amaze akoang mga co-teachers kay makabasa na siya. It is very fulfilling kay nakita nimu imong hard work dle lang na saakoa pati sa akoang mga kauban its actually a success, maka basa lang na silag 2-3 words lami na kaau na it’s a great improvement.” (IDI-01)

(I am very happy. Last time my student and I had a class here, my co-teachers were amazed because that student could already read. It is very fulfilling because you see not just my hard work but also the hard work of my co-teachers. It is actually a success, if they can read even just 2-3 words, it is a great improvement.)

Case 2 – Confident

Confident, not her real name is a reading coordinator at one secondary school in the Municipality of Kapalong. She is 32 years old.

When scaffolding non-reader students, she believed that we make sure that the students will feel safe and that they do not feel that they are different from the others; they will feel that they are being involved in a reading program wherein they are helped and not discriminated against. Also, she employs interactive learning activities and employs peer tutoring as a technique for scaffolding non-reader students.

Confident employs a variety of techniques and strategies to scaffold her non-reader students effectively. She recognizes that each student has unique reading needs, and thus carefully selects strategies that are tailored to suit these diverse requirements. Whether it's breaking down the basics of phonics, using visual aids, or incorporating interactive activities, she ensures that the chosen method aligns with the individual learning styles and challenges of her students

However, Confident acknowledges that she faces as a reading coordinator significant challenge in her efforts due to the lack of parental involvement. This lack of support from home makes it difficult for her students to reinforce what they've learned in the classroom, leading to slower progress. encouragement outside of school limits the effectiveness of her teaching strategies Confident continues to seek ways to bridge this gap, embracing individual differences of the learners and understanding that parental collaboration is crucial for the success of her non-reader students.

Research Question No. 1: What techniques and strategies are used by the reading coordinator when dealing with students who are non-readers?

To answer this research question, an in-depth interview was conducted with the participant, respectively. Hence, several sub-questions were asked about the techniques and strategies used by the reading coordinators when dealing with non-readers and were compressed

into three (3) emerging themes. The following themes are the: creating a positive class climate, employing interactive learning activities, and employing peer tutoring.

Creating Positive Class Climate

Building on mutual respect, encouragement, and a love of learning, this supportive environment gives non-readers the confidence and sense of worth they need to succeed in the future. When they are participating in a reading program where they are supported and not subjected to discrimination, non-readers feel safe and do not perceive themselves as being different from the others.

During the interview, Confident (pseudonym) share that in dealing with the students who are non-readers she still creating a positive environment for the students. She stated that by fostering a welcoming environment in the classroom for non-readers, teachers may assist students feel included and not discriminated against. She added that it is your responsibility as a teacher to ensure that students feel protected and do not perceive themselves different from other students. She stated that:

“We have to make sure that they feel safe and that they do not feel that they are different from the others, they would feel that they are being involved in a reading program wherein they are helped and not discriminated against.” (IDI-02)

(We need to ensure that they feel safe and do not feel different from others. They should feel included in a reading program where they are supported, not discriminated against.)

Employing Interactive Learning Activities

Incorporating interactive elements into instruction allows teachers to make the classroom more enjoyable and engaging for non-readers, which in turn motivates students to actively participate in their learning experience. Reading coordinators ensure that students are enjoying themselves while learning by gamifying the task to make it more interesting.

Confident (pseudonym) shares that by scaffolding non-reader students, she makes reading more engaging for her non-reader students. She said that for students to be interested in what they are learning and to enjoy themselves, interactive learning activities are essential. She stated that she used games to make learning entertaining and that she established a platform that enables students to have fun while learning. She said that:

“When I am teaching non-readers, I gamify the activity. I make it engaging by making sure that they’re having fun while learning. For instance, two years ago I initiated a program called ART (Activating Reading Techniques), and then during our activity there are art activities like, for example, associating words with pictures so that they would better understand the meaning of the word and not just be able to read it but also to comprehend it.” (IDI-02)

(When I teach non-readers, I turn the activity into a game. I make it engaging by ensuring they have fun while learning. For example, two years ago, I launched a program called ART (Activating Reading Techniques). During the activities, there are art elements, like associating words with pictures, so they can better understand the meaning of the word—not only to read it but also to comprehend it.)

Employing Peer Tutoring

Pairing non-readers with proficient readers emerges as an effective scaffolding strategy of reading coordinators. This peer-assisted approach allows non-readers to practice reading skills in a supportive and collaborative environment while observing and mimicking effective reading strategies. Such partnerships not only enhance literacy skills but also foster confidence and a sense of belonging among non-readers.

At this point, Confident (pseudonym) finds peer tutoring effective as an approach or strategy when scaffolding non-reading students to help them develop their literary skills.

Confident revealed that, as a reading coordinator, she employs peer tutoring as a technique for scaffolding non-readers. Partnership with those students who can read. She stated that:

“Partnership with those students who can read. Last time we had this peer strategy and technique, such as peer reading, wherein I asked the higher grade level students who are independent readers to teach the non-readers, so they had this 8-week program. I had to facilitate and observe the progress of the students. Those are the methods that have worked for me and are beneficial as well.” (IDI-02)

(Partnering with students who can read. Previously, we implemented a peer strategy, like peer reading, where I asked higher-grade students who are independent readers to teach the non-readers. This was part of an 8-week program, which I facilitated and monitored to observe the students’ progress. These methods have been effective and beneficial for me.)

Research Question No. 2: What are the lived experiences of the reading coordinators with non-reader students?

In the second question, the participant was asked about her lived experiences as a reading coordinator with non-reader students. Her responses underwent thematic analysis, and the researcher identified one emerging theme. The emerging idea that was formed is to observe a lack of parental involvement.

Observe Lack of Parental Involvement

Reading coordinators often encounter limited support from the parents of non-reader students because these parents may struggle with reading themselves. This literacy gap at home means parents is unable to assist or guide their children in reading activities, reinforcing the cycle of reading challenges for the students. This lack of support is one of the primary reasons why many students continue to struggle with or fail to develop basic reading skills.

During the interview, Confident (pseudonym) experienced no support from the parents of non-reader students, and it is because they themselves are non-readers. It was revealed that in scaffolding non-reader students, there is a lack of parental involvement that causes the learner to be a non-reader. Confident (pseudonym) states that they always find no parental figures there when they seek non-reader parents for support. She stated that:

“Most of these non-readers that we’ve had in the past and even until now, whenever we ask for support from their parents, we see that there is no parent involved. They cannot assist their children at home in reading because they themselves also have difficulty in reading, so that’s the number one most common reason why there are non-readers and struggling readers.” (IDI-02)

(Most of the non-readers we had, both in the past and even now, have parents who are not involved when we ask for support. They cannot assist their children with reading at home because they also struggle with reading themselves. This is the most common reason why there are non-readers and struggling readers.)

Research Question No. 3: What coping mechanisms do they employ to deal with the issue of scaffolding non-readers?

In the third question, the participant was asked what her coping mechanisms are that she employs to deal with the issues of scaffolding non-reader students. This includes the strategies, techniques, and steps she employs to face the challenges she encounters. In the response of the participant, the researcher identified three themes in the coding process, which are: prioritizing reading remediation, considering student’s background and situations, and using reward system.

Prioritizing Reading Remediation

Prioritizing work and establishing specific objectives are essential to effective management of time because they guarantee that the most important obligations receive the majority of one's attention. This frequently entails reading coordinators prioritizing reading remediation, even if doing so temporarily means putting other tasks on hold. They made an adjustment to prioritize reading remediation by bringing some documents home with me to work on.

During the interview, Confident (pseudonym) shares to overcome all the challenges as a reading coordinator is to consider prioritizing reading remediation for her students as a coping mechanism in dealing with the issues of scaffolding non-reader students. It was rendered clear during the in-depth interview that Confident disclosed that, as a teacher scaffolding non-reader student, you will give reading remediation first priority and that the paperwork will be brought home. She stated that:

“Adjustment on my own schedule, because I am a fully loaded teacher, I teach 6–8 subjects in a week, and I’m also a research teacher, and plus this one, I am a reading coordinator, so what I have to do is sacrifice my hours of paper work, I have to adjust it, make sure that I can accommodate them, my paper work I have to bring them at home cause I cannot bring the students home, so the students should be here and my paper work I bring it at home, so that’s how I made the adjustment, just like teachers bring their work at home because even during our vacant time we have to accommodate these students.” (IDI-02)

(I have to adjust my own schedule because I am a fully loaded teacher, teaching 6 to 8 subjects a week. I am also a research teacher and a reading coordinator. To manage everything, I sacrifice my paperwork hours; I have to adjust and ensure I can accommodate the students. I bring my paperwork home since I cannot take the students with me. The students need to be here, and my paperwork goes home with me. That is how I make these adjustments—just like other teachers who bring work home because even during our free time, we need to accommodate these students.)

Considering Student’s Background and Situations

Understanding students' current situations and backgrounds is crucial for effective intervention. With diverse needs and circumstances, reading coordinators must carefully assess each student's challenges to tailor suitable strategies. This individualized approach ensures that the methods employed address their specific reading needs, fostering progress and building a supportive learning environment for non-readers.

Confident (pseudonym) emphasized that students come from diverse backgrounds, each bringing unique experiences and needs into the classroom. She believes that understanding these individual differences is essential for effective scaffolding, particularly for non-readers. By considering each learner's specific circumstances, she tailors her scaffolding techniques to align with their unique needs, ensuring a more personalized and effective approach. She stated that:

“The first thing that we need to consider in addressing the needs of these non-reading students is that we need to make sure that the strategy that is selected for them is also suited to or appropriate to their reading needs because there are many diverse needs and situations.” (IDI-02)

(The first thing we need to consider in addressing the needs of non-reading students is ensuring that the strategy we select for them is suited to or appropriate for their reading needs, as there are many diverse needs and situations.)

Using Reward System

Providing rewards such as stickers, praise, or small prizes serves as a valuable motivational tool. These rewards offer positive reinforcement for even small achievements, encouraging non-readers to actively engage in reading activities. By giving students something to look forward to, coordinators foster a sense of accomplishment and sustained interest in literacy development.

At this point, Confident (pseudonym) shared that in coping with the issues of scaffolding non-readers, she utilizes a reward system in teaching her non-readers. She stated that she manages to cope by making sure that the students are given something to look forward to in attending classes with her; in that way, her students will attend and be motivated to learn with her in their reading sessions. She stated that:

“I manage to cope by making sure that they are given something to look forward to, for example, “do not be absent tomorrow because I’ll be giving rewards to those who will complete the activity and then plus points to your other subjects.” So that’s how I cope; the reward system is something that is still useful and effective as of this day.” (IDI-02)

(I manage to cope by ensuring that they have something to look forward to. For example, I tell them, ‘Do not be absent tomorrow because I will be giving rewards to those who complete the activity, plus points for your other subjects.’ That is how I cope; the reward system is still useful and effective to this day.)

Research Question No. 4: What are the insights of reading coordinators on scaffolding students who are non-readers?

To answer the last research question, an in-depth interview was conducted with the participant, respectively. Hence, several sub-questions were asked to provide her thoughts as a reading coordinator on scaffolding students who are non-readers. From her answers, the researcher identified the following main themes: embrace individual differences and gain a sense of fulfilment.

Embrace Individual Differences

Reading coordinators embrace the individual differences of non-reader students, understanding that each learner has unique strengths, challenges, and learning styles. They recognize that effective scaffolding requires tailoring instruction to meet the diverse needs of their students, which may include varying levels of cognitive ability, cultural backgrounds, and personal experiences with reading.

During the interview, Confident (pseudonym) shared that she, as a reading coordinator, felt that since every student is distinctive, it is important to take their differences into account. Confident shared that in scaffolding non-reader students, they need to consider individualized student traits for her to know the appropriate method to employ in teaching her non-reader students. In that way, she can tailor her teaching techniques to the student’s needs. She stated that:

“There are non-readers who just need one-on-one instruction; there are others who need instruction with the group; for example, they needed to be given a task as a group so that they would learn from others as well; and then there are also non-readers who lack memorization; they have difficulty in their memory; there are also others who have difficulty identifying the words and the sounds; so we have to make sure that each of the instructions given to them in terms of the approach is appropriate, making sure that their needs are addressed.” (IDI-02)

(Reading coordinators consider each student's background and circumstances when working with non-reader students. By understanding the different factors that contribute to their reading challenges, they can adjust their teaching strategies to meet individual needs effectively. This approach ensures that instruction is relevant and supportive, creating a more inclusive and effective learning environment.)

Gain a Sense of Fulfilment

Witnessing the progress and growth of these students, no matter how incremental, brings a deep satisfaction that reinforces their commitment to teaching. This sense of fulfillment often stems from the moments of breakthrough when a non-reader grasps a concept or successfully reads a passage for the first time, highlighting the impact of their support and guidance.

Confident (pseudonym) expressed that she found great fulfillment in teaching non-reader students, especially when witnessing their growth and improvement. She recounted a specific instance where her efforts made a significant impact on a non-reader, resulting in noticeable progress. This experience deeply resonated with her, reinforcing her passion and commitment to helping these students succeed. She stated that:

“I had this student very close to me during the reading remediation, and actually this student has an intellectual disability (ID). He really can only retain information for a shorter time, but there was an instance where I asked him to do a task and was able to execute it. That was the time that I realized that although he cannot read everything that a student at his level can read, he was able to successfully comprehend the most basic words, so that’s how I felt that I was successful during that time.” (IDI-02)

(I had a student who was very close to me during the reading remediation, and this student actually has an intellectual disability (ID).

He can only retain information for a short time, but there was a moment when I asked him to complete a task, and he was able to do it. That was when I realized that, although he cannot read everything that a student at his level can, he was able to successfully understand the most basic words. In that moment, I felt like I had achieved success.)

Case 3 – Simple

Simple, not her real name, is a female reading coordinator in one secondary school in the Municipality of Kapalong. She is 35 years old.

Simple's approach to teaching reading is comprehensive, as she integrates interactive learning activities to engage students and make learning enjoyable. She emphasizes teaching foundational skills, ensuring her students have a strong base to build upon. Additionally, she utilizes guided individual reading and peer tutoring to provide personalized support, helping non-reader students' progress at their own pace.

She observed that many non-reader students struggle with short attention spans and low retention, making it challenging for them to grasp and retain reading skills. Additionally, she noticed that these students often lack parental support, which is crucial for reinforcing learning outside the classroom.

Simple strongly believes that a solid reading foundation in elementary school is crucial for students' later success, and she ensures this by being a patient and dedicated reading coordinator. Her commitment to teaching is evident in her perseverance, even when faced with challenges. She finds great satisfaction and fulfillment in her role, especially when she witnesses her non-reader students making progress. Each step forward for her students reinforces her dedication to their learning journey.

Research Question No. 1: What techniques and strategies are used by the reading coordinator when dealing with students who are non-readers?

To answer this research question, an in-depth interview was conducted with the participant, respectively. Hence, several sub-questions were asked about the techniques and strategies used by the reading coordinators when dealing with non-readers. From her answers, the researcher identified the following main themes: employing interactive learning activities, going back to the basics, utilizing guided individual reading strategy, and employing peer tutoring.

Employing Interactive Learning Activities

One efficient method of involving non-reader pupils in the reading process and developing their literacy is to use interactive learning activities as a scaffolding strategy. Because various pupils have varied interests, some prefer to watch videos, while others prefer to listen. Apply additional strategies and use your creativity and simply implement tactics based on the child's ability.

During the interview, the researcher asks Simple (pseudonym) about her technique or strategy in order to make reading more engaging for students who find reading challenging, and she says that in order to address the various needs of the students, she, as a reading coordinator, implements diversified activities, such as games. She believed that students have different needs and want to be taught. She said that:

“You will feed them with differentiated activities not just in reading but mag hatag pud ka ug lahi lahi nga activity for example mga fun activity mga games, ug mga watching movies or videos. Apply more strategy because students has different likes lahi lahi silag gusto, nay uban students gusto mka kitag video naa puy uban gusto sila maminaw naa puy uban nga more on activities, be resourceful apply lang ang mga strategy depende sa capability sa bata.” (IDI-03)

(You will feed them with differentiated activities, not just in reading but also by providing different activities, for example, fun activities, games, and watching movies or videos. Apply more strategy because students have different likes, there are students who like to watch videos, and others just want to listen. Be resourceful and just apply strategies that will depend on the capabilities of the child.)

Going Back to the Basics

In scaffolding non-reader students, focusing on the basic skills required for reading, such as letter recognition and matching sounds, is essential. This approach, often referred to as "going back to the basics," helps students understand how letters combine to form words, which is crucial for decoding text. By establishing a solid foundation in these fundamental skills, reading coordinators enable students to gain the confidence and ability to tackle more complex reading tasks.

Simple (pseudonym) mentioned that she employs going back to basics in teaching non-reader students. Simple (pseudonym) believed that this technique was effective because in teaching non-reader students, the teaching process must be different compared to a normal class. This suggests that instruction with non-readers using a different method and adjusting to the learner's needs is effective in scaffolding non-readers. She stated that:

“To the students who are non-readers lahi jud ang mga process for example ang ilahang level, mas ginababa man gud namo, as for example, these non-readers naa sila ana na grade level possible ang among ginagamit nga reading material is kadtung mga bigginers

katung mga syllable lang mga alphabet recognition and alphabet sound.” (IDI-03)

(To the students who are non-readers, the teaching process is different, for example, we lowered the level as, for example, these non-readers are at that grade level possible we use those reading materials that are for beginners, like starting with the syllable, alphabet recognition, and alphabet sound.)

Utilizing Guided Individual Reading Strategy

In scaffolding non-reader students, reading coordinators can use the guided individual reading technique to address specific challenges by providing personalized, one-on-one reading sessions. This approach allows non-readers to receive tailored instruction that focuses on their unique needs. By progressing at their own pace, students can refine their skills and reinforce foundational reading abilities in a supportive environment.

Simple (pseudonym) also shared that she employs guided individual reading as a technique in scaffolding non-reader students. She explained that one-on-one reading sessions are particularly effective because they allow for more focused attention, providing the student work on specific areas of difficulty. This personalized approach ensures that each learner’s unique needs are addressed. She stated that:

“One on one reading, because you can give them more time, ma focusan nimu sila, kung asa ilang need, didtu nimu sila focussan.” (IDI-03)

(One-on-one reading because you can give them more time and you can focus on the things that is need to be addressed.)

Employing Peer Tutoring

Bringing non-reader students together with their peers is a valuable strategy in scaffolding literacy development. Through peer observation and practice, non-readers benefit from a nurturing environment where they can learn from each other and improve their skills collaboratively. This approach not only boosts their self-confidence but also fosters a sense of belonging, encouraging them to participate more actively in the learning process.

Simple (pseudonym) emphasized that by incorporating peer tutoring, she creates an opportunity for students to collaborate in group reading sessions, allowing them to share strategies and learn from one another. This approach fosters a supportive and inclusive environment where non-readers feel more comfortable, and ultimately making the scaffolding process more effective. She stated that:

“Group reading for example sila tanan pabasahon nako kay para dili siya ma ulaw so mag sundog sundog siya sa iyang mga classmate.” (IDI-03)

(Group reading, for example, all of them will read for the non-reader, not be shy, so that non-reader will just imitate their classmates.)

Research Question No. 2: What are the lived experiences of the reading coordinators with non-reader students?

In the second question, the participant was asked about her lived experiences as a reading coordinator with non-reader students. Her responses underwent thematic analysis, and the researcher identified one emerging theme. The emerging theme that was formed was: observe a lack of parental involvement and deal with a short attention span and low retention.

Observe Lack of Parental Involvement

One of the main causes of many pupils' continued difficulties or failure to acquire fundamental reading abilities is this lack of help. Parents of non-reader pupils often offer no help to reading coordinators since they may find reading difficult themselves. Because of this literacy gap at home, parents are unable to help or mentor their kids with reading activities, which feeds the pupils' cycle of reading difficulties.

During the interview, Simple (pseudonym) narrated her experience as a reading coordinator scaffolding non-reader students. She observed a lack of parental involvement in helping the non-reader students. She specifically mentioned that a lack of parental involvement is a barrier to scaffolding non-reader students. Once the child is a non-reader, there is something from the parent. She stated that:

“Barrier nga ma encounter sa bata kay at home, lack of attention from the parent aside ana hereditary, once ang bata dle kabalo mu basa naay something from the parent so most possible kining mga parent is dili pud kabalo mu basa in ana kay its very impossible nga mu abot ang bata sa grade 7 or in higher level nga dili kabalo mu basa wherein sa 6 years nga naa sila sa school more on reading sila and comprehension diba its very impossible.” (IDI-03)

(The barrier that we encounter with the students is at home, lack of attention from the parent, and aside from that, it is hereditary. Once the child is non-reader, there is something from the parent, so most likely, these parents are also non-readers because it is very impossible that the student is in grade 7 or at a higher level but still a non-reader, wherein in the 6 years that they are in school they are more on reading and comprehension, which is very impossible.)

Dealt with Short Attention Span and Low Retention

Reading coordinators often find that non-reader students struggle with short attention spans and low retention; they may read something one day only to forget it the next, requiring repeated sessions. This cycle can limit the students' ability to effectively retain reading material and make progress. Such challenges may result from early educational gaps where these students received limited support in developing foundational literacy skills.

Simple (pseudonym) highlighted that one of the significant challenges in scaffolding non-reader students was managing their short attention spans and low retention of information. She emphasized that these factors often make it difficult to maintain sustained focus during lessons and hinder long-term learning. As a result, she faces ongoing struggles in effectively scaffolding these students. She stated that:

“Our struggle is mga bata nga walay retention pabasahon nimu sila karun then the next day makalimot na sad sila so another session na pud of reading then the following day makalimot na sad sila because wala silay retention so lisod sila tudluan pag in ana.” (IDI-03)”

(Our struggle is those students who do not have retention, they will read now, then the next day they instantly forget, so another reading session again, then the following day they still forget, they do not have retention, so it is hard to teach if that is the case.)

Research Question No. 3: What coping mechanisms do they employ to deal with the issue of scaffolding non-readers?

In the third question, the participant was asked what coping mechanisms she employs to deal with the issues of scaffolding non-reader students. This includes the strategies, techniques, and steps she employs to face the challenges she encounters. In the response of the participant, the researcher identified three themes in the coding process, which are: prioritizing reading remediation; considering the student's background and situations; and being passionate about one's job.

Prioritizing Reading Remediation

Reading coordinators prioritize reading remediation with non-readers. Reading coordinators give their free time for the students to learn how to read. Instead of taking a break or doing something. For reading coordinators, this often means placing reading remediation at the forefront, even if it requires setting aside other duties temporarily. By dedicating time and resources to support non-reader students, coordinators create a structured approach to address literacy gaps.

During the interview, Simple (pseudonym) stated that she needs to make adjustments in her schedule to allocate more time for her non-reader students, emphasizing the importance of reading remediation. Simple mentioned that in focusing on helping these students improve their reading skills, she prioritizes reading remediation during her free time, even over completing paperwork. She stated that:

“Naa juy adjustment kay of course no sa isa ka adlaw we have 5 loads then we have 3 vacant loads so instead of making paper works gina gamit namo siya to teach the students on how to read dili siya lalim kay ginahatag nimu imohang free time para sa mga bata nga di kabalo mu basa instead of pwede ka makapahulay pwede ka makahimu ug lain nga activity, so naa jud siyay adjustment.” (IDI-03)

(There are adjustments. Of course, in a day we have 5 loads, then we have 3 vacant loads, so instead of making paper works, we use that time to teach the students how to read. It is not easy because you are giving your free time for the students to learn how to read. Instead of taking a break or doing something, that is why there is an adjustment.)

Considering Student's Background and Situations

Reading coordinators must have a deep understanding of their students' backgrounds and current circumstances. Given the diverse range of needs and situations, it is essential to consider how to address the specific challenges faced by non-readers and ensure that the chosen methods are suitable for their individual reading needs.

Simple (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of evaluating her students' backgrounds, believing that a thorough understanding of each student's unique situation is key to providing effective support.

As a reading coordinator, she stresses that knowing a student's background allows her to personalize her approach, ensuring the most appropriate help is given. She stated that:

“Syempre before you will give a remediation you will talk to the students para maka balo ka sa ilang background, importante man gud kung kabalo ka ilang background like iyang mama ug papa ba kabalo mu basa , sa ilang balay naa bay suga kung unsa ba sila ka pobrehon kay factor man pd gud ni siya kay kung in ana wala silay suga sa balay how they will practice reading or instead of having time to read mangita na lang kag panginabuhi kay para maka tabang ka sa pamlya so kinahanglan nimu siya e background check.” (IDI-03)

(Of course, before you give a remediation, you will talk to the students first for you to know their background. It is important to know their background, like if the parents know how to read, if they have electricity, and their way of life. Because it is a factor like the electricity, how can they practice reading if they do not have a source of light or instead of having time to read, they are busy finding work to help their family? That is why it is important to background check.)

Being Passionate about One's Job

Passionate reading coordinators consistently go above and beyond to create dynamic and supportive learning environments for their students. They continually seek out innovative strategies and resources tailored to the diverse needs of non-readers. Their commitment ensures that every student receives the individualized support, encouragement, and motivation necessary to thrive and make meaningful progress in their literacy journey.

Simple (pseudonym) expressed a profound passion for her work, viewing it as essential for overcoming the challenges of supporting non-reader students. She emphasized that teaching goes beyond merely delivering lessons; it requires a deep sense of care for each student. For her, having a genuine heart for the children is fundamental to fostering a positive and effective environment. She stated that:

“Factor pud nang naa kay kaluoy sa mga bata kay lahi man pud nang mag tudlo ka nga wala kay heart sa mga bata just plain teaching while kung naa kay heart para sa mga bata lahi imong tinudluan kay maningkamot ka unsaon pagpabasa sa ilaha.” (IDI-03)

(Sympathy for the students is also a factor, because your teaching is different if you do not have a heart for children; it is just plain teaching, while if you have a heart for the children, your teaching is different because you will work hard for them to learn how to read.)

Research Question No. 4: What are the insights of reading coordinators on scaffolding students who are non-readers?

To answer this research question, an in-depth interview was conducted with the participant. In the last set of questions, the participant was asked to provide her thoughts as a reading coordinator on scaffolding students who are non-readers. From her answers, the researcher identified the following main themes: give emphasis on the foundation, demonstrate unwavering patience, give more focus on reading, and gain a sense of fulfillment.

Give Emphasis on the Foundation

Reading coordinators emphasize the critical importance of establishing a solid literacy foundation early in a student's educational journey. Ideally, this foundation should be built during elementary school, where reading skills are a core focus of instruction. Without this early groundwork, students may encounter substantial challenges in high school, where the complexity of reading tasks increases and learning to read effectively becomes significantly more difficult.

During the interview, Simple (pseudonym) emphasized the significant role of focusing on the foundation of reading. She noted that students should learn to read in elementary school because it becomes challenging to teach them in high school if they graduate without this fundamental skill. She also believed that students should be assessed while they are still in elementary school. She stated that:

“Dapat ang ilahang foundation is strong so when we say foundation naa na siya sa elementary so dapat sa elementary pa lang e focus na sa mga bata ang reading kay kung mu graduate sila sa elementary nga dili kabasa lisod na para sa amoa dire nga mupabasa sa ilaha kay maglisod name, lisod na e train ang bata pag naa na dire although ma train namo pero dili na in ana ka kadako ang impact so dapat pag naa pa lang sa elementary dapat e assess na ang mga bata didtu sa elementary para as early as possible dapat ma assess na ang bata kay para kung makita nga naa nay reading efficiency.” (IDI-03)

(The foundation of the students must be strong, so when we say foundation, it is in elementary school, so children should focus on reading in elementary school because it will be difficult if they graduate without knowing how to read, it will be difficult to teach in high school. Yes, we can train them in high school, but the impact on them is not that much, better if when they were still in elementary school they were already assessed so that, as early as possible, we could see their reading efficiency.)

Demonstrate Unwavering Patience

Reading coordinators understand that each student progresses at their own pace, which is why they commit to providing the personalized time and support needed for each learner to master foundational reading skills. Patience is key, alongside a creative, adaptable approach tailored to the needs of non-readers. They continually seek innovative strategies and methods to effectively scaffold these students' literacy development.

Simple (pseudonym), becoming a reading coordinator demands a great deal of patience, as it involves working closely with students who struggle with reading. She emphasized the importance of thinking beyond the box, meaning that to effectively support non-reader students, one must develop creative and unconventional strategies that go beyond standard teaching methods. She said as follows:

“More patient, dapat mu think kag beyond the box kay para makabalo sila mu basa.” (IDI-03)

(More patient, and you need to think beyond the box for them to know how to read.)

Give More Focus on Reading

Reading coordinators emphasize the critical need to prioritize reading above all other subjects. Focusing on developing strong reading skills is essential, as students who struggle with reading face significant difficulties in comprehending material across other subjects.

Without a solid foundation in reading, learning in any classroom setting becomes increasingly challenging, hindering students' overall academic progress and success.

Simple (pseudonym) believed that placing a greater emphasis on reading was crucial to effectively supporting non-reader students. She suggested that in order to help these students improve more quickly, the focus should be exclusively on reading, without the distraction of other subjects. By concentrating solely on reading, Simple felt that students would be able to develop their skills more rapidly and confidently. She stated that:

“Focus on reading, reading without any other subjects kay nganu kung naay subjects its really useless gihapun kay unsaon nila pag sabot kung dili sila kabalo mu basa unsaon nila pagsabot dihaa sa sulod sa room a lain subject, so dapat reading sila magsugod.” (IDI-03)

(Focus on reading without any other subjects, because even if there are subjects, it is still useless because how could they comprehend inside the classroom if they do not know how to read? That is why they must focus on reading first.)

Gain a Sense of Fulfilment

Reading coordinators experience a deep sense of fulfillment when witnessing non-readers make progress, as it reflects the tangible results of their dedication and hard work. Each milestone, no matter how small whether it's a student mastering just a few words become a significant achievement. These moments of progress validate their continued efforts, reinforcing the value of their commitment to fostering each student's growth and success in literacy.

At this point, Simple (pseudonym) expressed immense joy in witnessing the progress of her non-reading students. She shared that by adopting a gradual, patient approach teaching students slowly and methodically she was able to significantly improve their reading skills. Watching her students develop their abilities over time filled her with a profound sense of fulfillment and satisfaction. She stated that:

“Just like my student before she's a girl then at first she doesn't really know how to read di jud siya kabalo so nag focus ko sa iyaha because we are applying one on one reading intervention so at first gi apply nko ang sounds so after almost 1 year non-reader gihapun siya kay naa pa mn mi sa sounds, the second year the following year nag blend name ug sound medyo happy nko kay at least maka blend na siya ug sound so the following year naga blending na gyud mi then tha third while naga blend mi mu adtu name samisa ka syllable so naa nay changes from non-reader to struggling reader.” (IDI-03)

(Just like my student before she is a girl, at first, she does not really know how to read, so I focus on that student because we are applying one-on-one reading intervention, so at first, I apply sounds, so after almost a year she is still a non-reader. The following year, we already blended sound. I am a bit happy at that time because at least she can blend sounds, so the following year we are still blending, and then the third year we proceed to syllables, so there are changes from non-reader to struggling reader.)

Case 4 – Approachable

Approachable, not her real name, is a female reading coordinator in one secondary school in the Municipality of Kapalong. She is 31 years old.

When scaffolding non-reader students, Approachable (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of treating them with respect and not making them feel inferior compared to their peers. She believes that it is crucial to create a supportive environment where these students do not feel discriminated against, as this can help build their confidence and motivation to learn.

One of the main barriers Approachable identified is the lack of self-confidence among non-reader students. Many of these students, especially those in high school, feel different from their peers because they struggle with reading. This lack of self-confidence can make it even harder for them to engage and improve their reading skills.

Approachable also pointed out that many students in secondary school have difficulty with reading because their foundational skills were not properly developed during elementary school. She stressed that a strong emphasis on reading instruction at the elementary level is essential for building a solid foundation that will support students throughout their educational journey.

Research Question No. 1: What techniques and strategies are used by the reading coordinator when dealing with students who are non-readers?

To answer this research question, an in-depth interview was conducted with the participant, respectively. Hence, several sub-questions were posed to explore the techniques and strategies used by reading coordinators in addressing non-readers' challenges. The responses were then analyzed and compressed into two emerging themes for better understanding. The following themes are: creating a positive class climate and employing interactive learning activities.

Creating Positive Class Climate

Reading coordinators establish a positive classroom environment as a key approach to supporting non-reader students. By creating a space where students feel included and valued, they promote a sense of belonging that enhances learning and prevents feelings of

inferiority. This welcoming atmosphere encourages inclusivity and fosters a supportive climate.

During the interview, Approachable (pseudonym) highlighted that creating a positive learning environment in the classroom is an effective strategy for scaffolding non-reader students. She emphasized that when students feel supported and valued, they are less likely to feel discriminated against or inferior compared to their peers, students also build confidence and improve reading skills more effectively. She said:

“Dle jud namo na sila gina discriminate, dle namo na sila ginapa feel nga they are inferior than the others so gina avoid jud namo na sila, as much as possible as reading teacher sa akoang mga non-reader mismo is gina pinangga nako sila sa room.” (IDI-04)”

(We really do not discriminate them, we would not make them feel inferior to the others, so we avoid it as much as possible. As a reading teacher to my non-readers, I care for them inside the classroom.)

Employing Interactive Learning Activities

In scaffolding non-reader students, reading coordinators use interactive activities like fun learning exercises to create an engaging classroom environment. By integrating these interactive components, teachers not only make learning enjoyable but also encourage non-readers to participate actively. This approach helps build their interest in reading, enhances their motivation, and fosters a sense of accomplishment, making it easier for them to overcome challenges and develop essential literacy skills.

Approachable (pseudonym) mentioned that one of her strategies for scaffolding non-reader pupils involves incorporating enjoyable activities alongside reading exercises. She believes that by making learning fun, students are more likely to engage with the material and stay motivated. This approach not only helps to improve their reading skills but also creates an enjoyable learning experience. She said that:

“Naa man mi Catch Up Friday no, one time is mag activities mi nga prior to reading dili lang gyud nga tutok sa reading, mag activities sa mi mga fun learning activities like that.” (IDI-04)

(We have Catch Up Friday, and one time, we have activities that are prior to reading, not just focused on reading, we have activities first that are fun, fun learning activities like that.)

Research Question No. 2: What are the lived experiences of the reading coordinators with non-reader students?

In the second question, the participant was asked about her lived experiences as a reading coordinator with non-reader students. Her responses underwent thematic analysis, and the researcher identified two emerging themes. The emerging themes that were formed are: encounter students who felt ashamed and dealt with short attention spans and low retention.

Observe Lack of Parental Involvement

In scaffolding non-reader students, reading coordinators often face the challenge of limited parental support, as many parents may also struggle with reading. To address this, coordinators emphasize the importance of actively collaborating with parents. This partnership is crucial for reinforcing reading skills at home, ensuring consistency in support, and creating an environment where non-readers can make progress both inside and outside the classroom.

During the interview, Approachable (pseudonym) shared her experience in scaffolding non-readers and discussed the significant challenge posed by the lack of parental support. Approachable stressed that fostering a strong partnership between teachers and parents is essential in providing the necessary encouragement and resources for non-readers to succeed. She stated that:

“Na learn nako nga dapat jud naay collaboration sa parents, if ang parent is dle sad kabalo mu basa dle maka tudlo dle maka reading remediate sa ilang anak at least man lang ma motivate nila ilang anak nga mag skwela every day, partnership with parents jud.” (IDI-04)

(I learned that we need the collaboration of the parents, and if the parent is also a non-reader, they cannot assist their child on how to read, they cannot have a reading remediation at home. But if they cannot teach reading, just at least motivate their child to go to school every day. We really need a partnership with the parents.)

Encounter Students Who Felt Ashamed

Non-reader students often feel shame and embarrassment about their reading difficulties, which can negatively impact their self-confidence. These emotions not only slow their learning progress but also harm their self-esteem and motivation to improve. As a result, addressing these feelings is crucial to supporting their overall development and success in reading.

Approachable (pseudonym) also shared that her non-reader students often feel ashamed during reading remediation sessions. She noted that this shame can severely undermine their self-confidence, making it even more challenging to engage them in the learning process. Self-esteem is critical, as their lack of confidence becomes a significant barrier in supporting their reading development. She stated that:

“Common nga barrier jud is ilahang lack of self-confidence kana gung high school na man gud sila ma ulaw na sila, therefore feel nila lahi sila sa uban, lahi sila sa kasagaran so murag ma ulaw sila inig everytime mag reading remiadiation mi especially if makakita ilahang mga classmate” (IDI-O4)

(The common barrier is their lack of self-confidence. Because they are already in high school, they feel that they are different from others. They feel ashamed every time we are doing reading remediation, especially when their classmate sees them.)

Research Question No. 3: What coping mechanisms do they employ to deal with the issue of scaffolding non-readers?

In the third question, the participant was asked what coping mechanisms she employs to deal with the issues of scaffolding non-reader students. This includes the strategies she employs to face the challenges she encounters. In the response of the participant, the researcher identified three themes, which are: prioritizing reading remediation, using reward systems, and being passionate about one’s job.

Prioritizing Reading Remediation

For reading coordinators, prioritizing reading remediation involves focusing on this effort above other tasks, sometimes setting aside additional responsibilities. By allocating dedicated time and resources, they establish a structured plan to help non-reader students bridge literacy gaps. This approach ensures targeted support to foster reading skills effectively.

During the interview, Approachable (pseudonym) expressed that her workload is overwhelming. Despite the demands, she prioritizes reading remediation over tasks like creating PowerPoints, recognizing the immediate impact that literacy support has on her students. Approachable emphasized that while other tasks are important, helping non-readers develop their skills takes precedence because it directly influences their academic success. She stated that:

“I am full work load kay kani laging gamay na lang atuang vacant time isa aka oras lang unya mu himu pa tag power point so unsa man atung unahaon ang power point nga e tudlo natu or ang pag remadiate. Usahay para ma free ko, para wala nakoy himuon sa akoang vacant time para mag remadiate na lang jud ko is sa balay naga himu nako daan ug powerpoint .” (IDI-04)

(I am full of work load because we have a short vacant time just one hour then we need to make a PowerPoint presentation, so what must we prioritize? Making power points or having a reading remediation. Sometimes, for me to have time for reading remediation in my vacant time, I am already making the power point at home.)

Using Reward System

By providing rewards like stickers, praise, or small prizes, teachers establish positive reinforcement for achievements, regardless of their size. This method motivates non-reader students to engage actively in reading activities and cultivates a sense of accomplishment as they achieve specific goals. Such recognition boosts their confidence and encourages continued participation in learning.

Approachable (pseudonym) believes that offering rewards is an effective strategy to combat student boredom and keep them engaged in the classroom. She observed that many students easily lose interest during lessons, so she incorporates rewards as a way to reignite their motivation and encourage active participation. She said as follows:

“Pag mag pabasa they will tend to be bored, bored na sila and they will not listen to you anymore so mao tu naa koy mga pakulo, padula , pa unhanay mao tu na ma motivate sila kay kung kinsay maka una naay reward they will receive something then pasalida about anang reading pod , basa basa gihapun.” (IDI-04)

(In reading sessions, they will tend to be bored, and they will not listen to you anymore, so I have tricks and games. For them to be motivated is we have a reward system in which they will receive something.)

Being Passionate about One’s Job

Passionate reading coordinators often go the extra mile to foster engaging and supportive learning environments for their students. They understand that they play a crucial role in students' literacy development and feel responsible if a student struggles with reading. This accountability drives them to implement effective strategies and provide the necessary support to help every student succeed.

At this point, Approachable (pseudonym) emphasized that reading coordinators play a crucial role in ensuring non-readers receive the necessary scaffolding and support as they work to develop their reading skills. Additionally, Approachable highlighted that teachers are ultimately accountable for their students' reading abilities. She stated that:

“Atuang obligasyon ang mga estudyante it is our duty, it is our responsibility ug tulubagon natu kung dle sila makabasa kay reading teacher man ta so atua sila dapat e remediate.” (IDI-04)

(The students are our obligations, it is our duty, it is our responsibility, and we are accountable if they do not know how to read because we are a reading teacher, so we need to have a reading remediation for them.)

Research Question No. 4: What are the insights of reading coordinators on scaffolding students who are non-readers?

To answer this research question, an in-depth interview was conducted with the participant. In the last set of questions, the participant

was asked to provide her thoughts as a reading coordinator on scaffolding students who are non-readers. From her answers, the researcher identified the following main themes: give emphasis on the foundation, demonstrate unwavering patience, give more focus on reading, embrace individual differences, and gain a sense of fulfillment.

Give Emphasis on the Foundation

Reading coordinators understand that teaching reading becomes more difficult when students enter secondary school without a strong foundation in basic literacy skills, making early intervention in elementary school crucial. By focusing on developing these foundational skills during the early years, they aim to equip students for long-term success in reading. This proactive approach helps ensure that students are better prepared for the demands of higher-level learning.

During the interview, Approachable (pseudonym) expressed that teaching reading at the secondary level is particularly challenging, as students at this stage often struggle with foundational skills they should have acquired earlier. She emphasized the importance of students learning to read in elementary school, where there is more time to build these essential skills. She stated that:

“Mas maayu pa nga elementary nga bata or beginning readers akong tudluan kaysa sa kaning ni abot nag high school, ug sa elementary mn jud dapat na sila maka balo ug basa.” (IDI-04)

(It is better if I teach elementary students, or those who are beginning readers, rather than high school level students, and besides, it really must be in elementary where they learn reading.)

Demonstrate Unwavering Patience

Reading coordinators recognize that every student learns at their own pace and are dedicated to offering the time and support needed for all learners to master fundamental reading skills. Managing non-reader students can be challenging, making patience a crucial quality in effectively supporting their development. This patience enables coordinators to create a nurturing environment that fosters growth and progress in reading.

Approachable (pseudonym) also said that scaffolding non-reader pupils demands a great deal of patience, as progress can be slow and the challenges are often complex. Approachable emphasized that handling non-reader students is far from easy, requiring a deep commitment and a persistent effort to help them overcome their reading difficulties. She stated that:

“Let’s be patient in dealing with them and lets bear in mind that they are our responsibility. Dle lalim usahay maka ingun ko nga mas maayu pa nga elementary nga bata or beginning readers akong tudluan kaysa sa kaning ni abot nag high school kay ilaha man gung interest usahay ang atuang mahit ilahang self-confidence mao nang usahay dle sila willing so I think dle jud siya lalim.” (IDI-04)

(Let us be patient in dealing with them and keep in mind that they are our responsibility. It is not easy, and sometimes it is better to teach elementary students or those who are beginners in learning reading than to teach students who are in high school because we sometimes hit their interest and self-confidence. That is why sometimes they are not willing to learn. That is why it is not easy.)

Give More Focus on Reading

Prioritizing tasks and setting clear objectives are vital for effective time management, ensuring that the most important responsibilities receive adequate attention. For reading coordinators, this often means focusing on reading remediation as a primary objective. By doing so, they can allocate their time and resources effectively to support non-reader students and address literacy gaps.

According to Approachable (pseudonym), teachers should prioritize reading remediation because it addresses need of their students—developing essential literacy skills. She believes teachers need to focus more on reading. Approachable emphasized that reading is foundational to academic success, and therefore, it should be given precedence over other activities in the classroom. She stated that:

“Mas maayu pa nga elementary nga bata or beginning mao na amoang kinahanglan sa pagka karun sa high school.” (IDI-04)

(Teachers will focus on reading remediation, which is what we need here in high school.)

Embrace Individual Differences

Reading coordinators value the individual differences among non-reader students, recognizing that each learner possesses unique strengths, challenges, and learning styles. They understand that effective scaffolding necessitates adapting instruction to address the diverse needs of their students, which can include different levels of cognitive ability, cultural backgrounds, and personal experiences with reading.

Approachable (pseudonym) believes that every child has different abilities it’s important to consider this when helping them. She emphasized the need to approach each student with an open mind, recognizing that not all students are naturally good at reading. Approachable pointed out that some students come from less fortunate backgrounds, which can affect their ability to read, so it’s crucial to be understanding and supportive in addressing their needs. She stated that:

“Dawat dawat pero with an open heart with an open mind let’s just accept nga dle jud tanan estudyante blessed with the ability to read

na dayun kay naa juy mga disadvantage students mga less fortunate students so atua na silang obligasyon, atua na silang responsibilidad so let's do our part na lang , d na mag kwenta.” (IDI-04)

(We need to accept with an open mind that not every student is blessed with the ability to read because we have less fortunate students, and they are our obligation and responsibility, so let us do our part.)

Gain a Sense of Fulfilment

Observing the progress and growth of these students, regardless of how small, provides a profound sense of satisfaction that strengthens their commitment to teaching. This fulfillment often arises during breakthrough moments when a non-reader comprehends a concept or reads a passage successfully for the first time, emphasizing the positive influence of their support and guidance.

At this point, Approachable (pseudonym) shared that helping a student who cannot read become a reader makes her feel really proud and satisfied. She finds great joy in seeing the progress these students make and the difference it can make in their lives. For Approachable (pseudonym), turning a non-reader into a reader is one of the most rewarding parts of her job. She stated that:

“There was a time last year natutukan jud nako, babae tu siya natutukan nako siya at first napansin nako nganga jud siya dle pa jud siya kabalo ug sounds kaayu ang uban sounds sa letter kay malimtan pa niya, later on kay gi tutukan man nako mga at least once a week mi magkita and murag willing man pud siya to learn how to read as in pag end sa school year kay though nganga pa gihapun siya pero makabasa na gyud siya dle na jud siya non-reader.” (IDI-04)

(There was a time last year I focused on that one student, she is a girl. At first, I noticed that she really did not know the sounds of the letters, but because I focused on her at least once a week, we saw each other, and I noticed that she had a willingness to learn how to read, and at the end of the school year, though she could not utter the words properly, she could already read, she is not a non-reader anymore.)

Case 5- Enthusiastic

Enthusiastic, not her real name, is a female reading coordinator in one secondary school in the Municipality of Kapalong, she is 30 years old.

When helping non-reader students, she focuses on using fun and engaging activities to make learning interesting. She often goes back to the basics of reading, like teaching letter sounds and simple words. She also spends time reading with each student individually, guiding them step by step. This approach helps her build confidence and improve their reading skills over time.

Enthusiastic shared the difficulties she faces when helping non-reader students. She often deals with students who feel embarrassed about not being able to read, which makes them shy away from learning. Many of these students also have a hard time focusing on lessons and quickly forget what they've learned. These challenges make it tough to keep them engaged and help them progress. Nevertheless, she overcomes the challenges by staying passionate about her work as a reading coordinator.

She admitted the need of one-on-one with each student for guided reading. This personalized attention helps address their specific needs and challenges. As a reading coordinator, she also believes it's essential to consider each student's individual differences to support their learning effectively.

Research Question No. 1: What techniques and strategies are used by the reading coordinator when dealing with students who are non-readers?

To answer this research question, an in-depth interview was conducted with the participant, respectively. Hence, several sub-questions were asked about the techniques and strategies used by the reading coordinators when dealing with non-readers. From her answers, the researcher identified the following main themes: employing interactive learning activities, going back to the basics, and utilizing a guided individual reading strategy.

Employing Interactive Learning Activities

One efficient method of involving non-reader pupils in the reading process and developing their literacy is to use interactive learning activities as a scaffolding strategy. Because various pupils have varied interests, some prefer to watch videos, while others prefer to listen. Apply additional strategies and use your creativity and simply implement tactics based on the child's ability.

During the interview, Enthusiastic (pseudonym) explained that she uses games as a way to help non-reader students learn. She believes that making learning fun through games can make reading less intimidating for them. She also lets her students watch videos about reading to keep them interested. To make it even more exciting, she adds a fun challenge while they learn to read. She said that:

“Sometimes I do the gaming, gaming strategy kay ma lingaw pud sila, sometimes I allow them to watch mga clips about sa reading. Naa koy mga pakulo, padula, pa unhanay mao tu na ma motivate sila kay kung kinsay maka una naay reward they will receive something then pasalida about anang reading pod, basa basa gihapun.” (IDI-05)

(Sometimes I do the gaming, gaming strategy allows them to enjoy it, and sometimes I allow them to watch clips about reading. I have

something to offer, like games, like a contest where whoever wins has a reward and will receive something, then watching videos about reading, still reading.)

Going Back to the Basics

In scaffolding non-reader students, reading coordinators prioritize foundational skills, starting with letter recognition and their corresponding sounds. This critical step helps students understand how letters form words, enabling them to decode text. Building these foundational skills is essential for fostering long-term reading success and empowering students to advance in their literacy journey.

Enthusiastic (pseudonym) mentioned that many students have a hard time recognizing letters, so she goes back to teaching them phonemic awareness. She focuses on the basics, like helping them understand the sounds that letters make. By starting from the beginning, she helps her non-reading students build a stronger foundation in reading. She said as follows:

“Nibalik man ko, based on my own experience nibalik ko ug phonemic awareness cause they don’t even identify letters so what I did was nibalik kog phonemic awareness and the instructions mother tongue gyud and uttering the words correctly with correct pronunciations ana siya ang nahitabo.” (IDI-05)

(Based on my own experience, I came back to phonemic awareness because they do not even identify letters, so what I did was teach phonemic awareness, and the instructions were in mother tongue, and uttering the words correctly with correct pronunciations that is what happened.)

Utilizing Guided Individual Reading Strategy

Using the guided individual reading technique gives reading coordinators more time to concentrate on the issues that need to be addressed. Individual must direct their own guided individual reading method because they will not learn to read if they are not guided. With this individualized attention, the learner can practice at their own pace, strengthening foundational skills and boosting confidence.

Enthusiastic (pseudonym) also uses an individual reading strategy to help her non-reader students. She believes that one-on-one reading sessions are the most effective way to teach these students. By working with them individually, she can focus on their specific needs and guide them step by step. This personalized approach has proven to be the best method for helping her non-reader students improve. She said:

“Guided individual reading strategy, guided individual gyud kay kung way mu guide sa ilaha di sila kabasa, as in sila gyud one on one gyud mo, moa ng pinaka effective nga strategy.” (IDI-05)

(A guided individual reading strategy must be guided by the individual because if no one guides them, they will not learn how to read. It is really a one-on-one strategy that is the most effective.)

Research Question No. 2: What are the lived experiences of the reading coordinators with non-reader students?

In the second question, the participant was asked about her lived experiences as a reading coordinator with non-reader students. Her responses underwent thematic analysis, and the researcher identified the following emerging themes that formed: encounter students who felt ashamed and dealt with a short attention span and low retention.

Encounter Students Who Felt Ashamed

In scaffolding non-reader students, reading coordinators must address the emotional barriers of shame and embarrassment that often accompany reading difficulties. These feelings can cause students to avoid participating in reading remediation, hindering their progress. By offering encouragement and empathy, they help alleviate negative emotions, fostering a positive mindset that encourages active participation and ultimately enhances reading development.

During the interview, Enthusiastic (pseudonym) shared that some students feel too embarrassed about not being able to read, so they stop coming to their reading sessions. She explained that, despite her efforts to encourage the student, she cannot force them to return. Even though she reassures the student, their shame about being a non-reader keeps them from not coming back. She said as follows:

“Grade 8 na mn siya run ma ulaw na siya mu balik dre, d kaayu nko ma force bisag sige nakog ingnon di na man mu balik kay ma ulaw.” (IDI-05)

(That student is already in Grade 8, and she feels ashamed going back here. I really cannot force her, even though I always tell her, but she will not come back because she feels ashamed.)

Dealt with Short Attention Span and Low Retention

Non-reader children usually has short attention spans and poor memory, necessitating repeated sessions because they may read something one day and forget it the next. This pattern may hinder the pupils' capacity to learn and advance their reading skills. Early educational gaps that left these pupils with little assistance in acquiring the fundamentals of literacy may be the cause of these difficulties.

Enthusiastic (pseudonym) also mentioned that many non-reader students struggle to retain the lessons she teaches. She explained that these students often have short attention spans, making it hard for them to stay focused during reading activities. Additionally, their cognitive processing is slower, so it takes them longer to grasp reading concepts. These challenges make it more difficult for them to make steady progress in learning to read. She stated that:

“Kadtu short period of attention span and then dugay masulod sa ilang utok gyud , magbalik na mi lang A-D nami karun na simana pagka sunod nga simana unsa ni nga letter nalimtan na pud kadtu siya ang span sa ilang attention is gamay at the same time ang cognitive process nila dili musulod sa ilang utok ilag gi estadihan.” (IDI-05)

(Their short period of attention span and then it takes long for them to learn. I will tell them to take vitamins, we are in letter A-D this week, and then next week I will ask them what that letter is, but they already forgot. Also, they have a short attention span, and at the same time, their cognitive process is slow.)

Research Question No. 3: What coping mechanisms do they employ to deal with the issue of scaffolding non-readers?

In the third question, the participant was asked what her coping mechanisms are that she employs to deal with the issues of scaffolding non-reader students. This includes the strategy, techniques, and steps she employs in facing the challenges she encounters. In the response of the participant, the researcher identified the following theme in the coding process, which is: being passionate about one’s job.

Being Passionate about One’s Job

Their passion drives them to seek out creative strategies and resources tailored to the diverse needs of non-readers, ensuring that each student receives the guidance and encouragement necessary for growth. Dedicated reading coordinators often go the extra mile to create engaging and supportive learning environments for their students

During the interview, Enthusiastic (pseudonym) shared that she has a deep passion for teaching non-readers and genuinely enjoys helping them learn to read. Her love for teaching drives her to overcome the many challenges that come with supporting non-reader students. Because she truly loves what she does, she finds joy in managing the difficulties and seeing her students make progress. She said as follows:

“I just manage it well because I love teaching them reading, it’s my passion. I am so happy doing this every day. I’m so glad in every progress that I encounter with the students, and I am happy upon doing all of those things.” (IDI-05)

(I just manage it well because I love teaching them reading—it’s my passion. I am so happy doing this every day. I am glad with every bit of progress I see in the students, and I feel happy doing all of these things.)

Research Question No. 4: What are the insights of reading coordinators on scaffolding students who are non-readers?

To answer the last research question, an in-depth interview was conducted with the participant, respectively. Hence, several sub-questions were asked to provide her thoughts as a reading coordinator on scaffolding students who are non-readers. From her answers, the researcher identified the following main themes: give more focus on reading, embrace individual differences, and gain a sense of fulfillment.

Give More Focus on Reading

In scaffolding non-reader students, reading coordinators understand the importance of prioritizing reading development, as strong reading skills are essential for learning across all subjects. By dedicating time to one-on-one guided reading sessions, coordinators provide targeted support tailored to each student’s needs. This individualized approach helps build foundational reading skills, allowing students to gain the confidence and ability necessary to succeed academically.

During the interview, Enthusiastic (pseudonym) emphasized that reading coordinators should spend more time focusing on non-readers individually, as blending them with students who can already read hinders their progress. She believes that one-on-one reading sessions are essential for helping these students catch up and improve their skills. She stated that:

“Give time one on one a guided reading, spend time one on one in a guided reading kay kung e halo nimu na siya dha sa kabalo na mu basa wa jud nay pprogress tagaan jug time nga siya lang one on one siya.” (IDI-05)

(Give time one-on-one for guided reading; spend time one-on-one for guided reading because if you blend them with students who know how to read, there is no progress. You must give your students time to have a one-on-one reading.)

Embrace Individual Differences

Reading coordinators value the individual differences among non-reader students, recognizing each student’s unique strengths, challenges, and learning preferences. They understand that effective support means adapting instruction to accommodate diverse needs, such as cognitive levels, cultural backgrounds, and prior reading experiences. This tailored approach is essential for fostering student’s growth.

Enthusiastic (pseudonym) also strongly believes that it's important to recognize and respect individual differences in students, especially when teaching non-readers. She understands that each student's brain works differently, and this affects how they learn to read. By considering these unique learning styles and needs, she tables to help her non-reader students. She stated that:

“Sometimes naay mga time nga kana ganing ma kuan naka unsa man ning bataa ni pero di biya natu ma pugos naa man ko ana nga principles consider individual differences lahi lahi gyud tag utok sa process.” (IDI-05)

(Sometimes we wonder what this kind of student is, but we cannot force them. I have that kind of principle: consider individual differences; everyone's brain processes differently.)

Gain a Sense of Fulfilment

Reading coordinators experience profound fulfillment in witnessing the progress of non-readers, knowing their efforts have truly made a difference. Even when a student masters just a few new words, it marks an important milestone, underscoring the impact of their dedication and persistence. These small but meaningful victories reaffirm the positive influence they have and inspire them to continue supporting non-readers.

At this point, Enthusiastic (pseudonym) expressed pride in her role as a reading coordinator because she has made a significant impact on her students' lives. She feels accomplished for successfully helping non-readers become readers. Seeing her students improve and gain confidence in their reading skills brings her a great sense of satisfaction and achievement. She stated that:

“I’m so proud of myself, out of 24 isa ra jud ang di na kabasa. I’m so proud of myself nga I contributed a lot sa ilahang future sa mga kadtu na mga bata I was wondering before kung kaya kaha ni pero grabe gyud na kaya ra gyud ang all.” (IDI-05)

(I am so proud of myself, out of 24 non-readers, there is only one student who remains a non-reader. I am so proud of myself because I contributed a lot to their future. I was wondering before if I could do it, but I manage everything.)

Cross-Case Analysis

This study utilized a qualitative research design using case study approach, tempering to make sense of, or interpret phenomena in terms of the meanings people bring to them, aiming to understand why people think, feel, react and behave in the way they do. We employ a case study method to collect information about respondent's experience on overcoming the reentry of person deprived of liberty in the community (Talbot, 2015).

In addition, case studies have been largely used in the social sciences and have been found to be especially valuable in practice-oriented fields (such as criminology, education, management, and social work). It is understood that this case study design is a genuine manner of representing the realities that the participant's experience in their lives, giving deeper understanding of the current psychological phenomena. Thus, interviews allow the researchers to address the phenomenon profoundly, providing a space of aperture for the informants to express their experiences in detail, approaching reality as faithfully as possible. It is to understand the essence of the experience that participants share within a common ground. Hence, participants will bring out their subjective and objective experience (Mills, Durepos, et al, 2010).

We presented the different cases and the themes that emerged within the data gathered. It is followed with the cross-case analysis where we created the themes in which will be used in the study. This is for the extent that the patterns found in the data from each interviews matched the early interpretation of the process that had been developed so as that the internal validity of that interpretation is strengthened (Zach, 2006).

In this section we presented the similarities and the differences of the themes that had emerged in case-to-case basis.

In the previous sections, I presented the different themes from each case, deriving from the analyzed data gathered from the respondents. the result was based on the answers of the participants on the four research questions regarding participant's techniques and strategies, experiences in scaffolding non-readers, how do they cope with their experiences and their insights in scaffolding non-reader students.

Research Question No. 1: What techniques and strategies are used by the reading coordinator when dealing with students who are non-readers?

To answer this research question, in-depth interviews were conducted with the participants. Several sub-questions were asked to unveil the techniques and strategies that are used by the reading coordinators in scaffolding non-reader students.

Five main ideas became very clear. The first big idea that came up was about creating a positive class climate. This means making the classroom a place where everyone feels welcomed, respected, and safe. When students feel good about being in class, they are more likely to learn and participate. The second idea was about using interactive learning activities. This means doing things in class that get everyone involved, like group discussions or hands-on projects. It is a fun way to learn because everyone can join in and share their ideas.

The third theme was going back to the basics. This means focusing on the most important things in learning, like reading, writing, and math. Returning to foundational skills helps establish a solid base for learning. Building from the basics strengthens the core

understanding necessary for further progress. The fourth idea was about using a guided individual reading strategy. Finally, the fifth theme focused on using peer tutoring, which involves encouraging students to support each other's learning. When students assist in teaching each other, they enhance their own understanding while also fostering strong bonds with classmates. This collaborative approach fosters not only academic growth but also strengthens social bonds, encouraging positive peer interactions and mutual support.

Table 2. Techniques and Strategies Used by The Reading Coordinators

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Creating Positive Class Climate	<p>"We will not refer to them as non-readers or struggling readers; instead, we will explain that they are part of a reading program because we see potential in them. I know they already have an idea of why they are in the reading program, but as a teacher, it is important to build their confidence so they do not feel left behind." -IDI-01</p> <p>"We have to make sure that they feel safe and that they do not feel that they are different from the others, they would feel that they are being involved in a reading program wherein they are helped and not discriminated against." -IDI-02</p> <p>"We really do not discriminate them, we would not make them feel inferior to the others, so we avoid it as much as possible. As a reading teacher to my non-readers, I care for them inside the classroom." -IDI-04</p>
Employing Interactive Learning Activities	<p>"We also incorporate games, activities, or play, not just literal activities. We need to be hands-on, not just always reading they also need to manipulate objects and paper, because when you tell them to read something just by pointing it, they will not appreciate the learning process." -IDI-01</p> <p>"When I am teaching non-readers, I gamify the activity. I make it engaging by making sure that they're having fun while learning. For instance, two years ago I initiated a program called ART (Activating Reading Techniques), and then during our activity there are art activities like, for example, associating words with pictures so that they would better understand the meaning of the word and not just be able to read it but also to comprehend it." -IDI-02</p> <p>"You will feed them with differentiated activities, not just in reading but also by providing different activities, for example, fun activities, games, and watching movies or videos. Apply more strategy because students have different likes, there are students who like to watch videos, and others just want to listen. Be resourceful and just apply strategies that will depend on the capabilities of the child." -IDI-03</p> <p>"We have Catch Up Friday, and one time, we have activities that are prior to reading, not just focused on reading, we have activities first that are fun, fun learning activities like that." -IDI-04</p> <p>"Sometimes I do the gaming, gaming strategy allows them to enjoy it, and sometimes I allow them to watch clips about reading. I have something to offer, like games, like a contest where whoever wins has a reward and will receive something, then watching videos about reading, still reading." -IDI-05</p>
Going Back to Basics	<p>"Use easy activities, the basics, before proceeding to more complicated ones. You must use unified or simplified instructions. You would start from the basics; you would start recognizing letters and sounds. It is better that they know how to read than teach them lessons because they still cannot comprehend the lessons if they do not know how to read." -IDI-01</p> <p>"To the students who are non-readers, the teaching process is different, for example, we lowered the level as, for example, these non-readers are at that grade level possible we use those reading materials that are for beginners, like starting with the syllable, alphabet recognition, and alphabet sound." -IDI-03</p> <p>"Based on my own experience, I came back to phonemic awareness because they do not even identify letters, so what I did was teach phonemic awareness, and the instructions were in mother tongue, and uttering the words correctly with correct pronunciations that is what happened." -IDI-05</p>
Utilizing Guided Individual Reading Strategy	<p>"Not all students want to learn with other students; there are students who want to learn with only the teacher and student. That is one of the struggles because you cannot force the student because it might affect their interest in learning, that is why you just do not make that student learn with other students." -IDI-01</p> <p>"One-on-one reading because you can give them more time and you can focus on the things that is need to be addressed." -IDI-03</p> <p>"A guided individual reading strategy must be guided by the individual because if no one guides them, they will not learn how to read. It is really a one-on-one strategy that is the most effective." -IDI-05</p>
Employing Peer Tutoring	<p>"You need to collaborate with other readers of the same level, they would share and learn together. Use peer tutoring, I ask independent readers to teach them." -IDI-01</p> <p>"Partnership with those students who can read. Last time we had this peer strategy and technique, such as peer reading, wherein I asked the higher grade level students who are independent readers to teach the non-readers, so they had this 8-week program. I had to facilitate and observe the progress of the students. Those are the methods that have worked for me and are beneficial as well." -IDI-02</p> <p>"Group reading, for example, all of them will read for the non-reader, not be shy, so that non-reader will just imitate their classmates" -IDI-03</p>

The major themes and core ideas for research question number 1 were presented in Table 2. From the answers of the participants, five major themes emerged: Creating Positive Class Climate, Employing Interactive Learning Activities, Going Back to the Basics, Utilizing Guided Individual Reading Strategy, and Employing Peer Tutoring.

Creating a Positive Class Climate

Using a strategy of supporting non-reader children, reading coordinators establish a positive classroom environment. Fostering a welcoming environment and using inclusive teaching practices aim to establish a learning environment that maximizes learning by connecting students to the content and helping them feel like they belong. Positive classroom dynamics increase students' propensity

to engage with the topic and think critically about it. Given the diverse range of individuals in classrooms, educators work hard to engage every student and spark their interest in reading.

Smart (pseudonym) discussed her methods for supporting students who struggle with reading, emphasizing the importance of maintaining a positive learning environment. One of her key strategies is to avoid labeling her students as "non-readers," a choice she makes to build their confidence and prevent them from feeling inferior. Smart aims to foster a sense of belonging and motivation among her students. She said:

"We will not be calling them non-readers or struggling readers, we just explain that they are part of a reading program, and we choose them because we see potential in them. I know they already have an idea why they are part of the reading program, but as a teacher, you also need to establish confidence in your students so they will not feel behind." (IDI-01)

(We will not refer to them as non-readers or struggling readers; instead, we will explain that they are part of a reading program because we see potential in them. I know they already have an idea of why they are in the reading program, but as a teacher, it is important to build their confidence so they do not feel left behind.)

Additionally, Confident (pseudonym) share that in dealing with the students who are non-readers she still creating a positive environment for the students. She stated that by fostering a welcoming environment in the classroom for non-readers, teachers may assist students feel included and not discriminated against. She added that it is your responsibility as a teacher to ensure that students feel protected: She stated that:

"We have to make sure that they feel safe and that they do not feel that they are different from the others, they would feel that they are being involved in a reading program wherein they are helped and not discriminated against." (IDI-02)

(We need to ensure that they feel safe and do not feel different from others. They should feel included in a reading program where they're supported, not discriminated against.)

Moreover, Approachable (pseudonym) highlighted that creating a positive learning environment in the classroom is an effective strategy for scaffolding non-reader students. She emphasized that when students feel supported and valued, they are less likely to feel discriminated against or inferior compared to their peers, students also build confidence and improve their reading skills more effectively. She said:

"Dle jud namo na sila gina discriminate, dle namo na sila ginapa feel nga they are inferior than the others so gina avoid jud namo na sila, as much as possible as reading teacher sa akoang mga non-reader mismo is gina pinangga nako sila sa room." (IDI-04)

(We really do not discriminate them, we would not make them feel inferior to the others, so we avoid it as much as possible. As a reading teacher to my non-readers, I care for them inside the classroom.)

Employing Interactive Learning Activities

Through the use of interactive learning, a teacher can create a classroom that is more engaging and joyful, inspiring students to come to class ready to learn how to read. Interactive learning is a hands-on, immersive method of teaching and learning in which students actively participate in their education. Its main advantage is that it nurtures a spirit of inquiry and critical thinking in students, encouraging them to question, analyze, and explore ideas deeply.

Smart (pseudonym) shares that in scaffolding non-reader students, she employs interactive learning activities. She said that for students to be interested in what they are learning and to enjoy themselves, interactive learning activities are essential. Activities allow students to stay engaged in their learning. She discussed how crucial it is to use interactive learning activities to keep kids interested and having fun while learning. She Shared:

"We also incorporate mga game activities or play not use literal activities dapat hands on gyud na sila di lang na sila basa ug basa they also need to manipulate objects and paper kay ug mu ingon kag basaha ni tudlo tudlo lang ka they will not appreciate the learning process." (IDI-01)

(We also incorporate games, activities, or play, not just literal activities. We need to be hands-on, not just always reading they also need to manipulate objects and paper, because when you tell them to read something just by pointing it, they will not appreciate the learning process.)

Also, Confident (pseudonym) shares that by scaffolding non-reader students, she makes reading more engaging for her non-reader students. She said that for students to be interested in what they are learning and to enjoy themselves, interactive learning activities are essential. She stated that she used games to make learning entertaining and that she established a platform that enables students to have fun while learning. She said that:

"When I am teaching non-readers, I gamify the activity. I make it engaging by making sure that they're having fun while learning. For instance, two years ago I initiated a program called ART (Activating Reading Techniques), and then during our activity there are art activities like, for example, associating words with pictures so that they would better understand the meaning of the word and not just

be able to read it but also to comprehend it.” (IDI-02)

(When I teach non-readers, I turn the activity into a game. I make it engaging by ensuring they have fun while learning. For example, two years ago, I launched a program called ART (Activating Reading Techniques). During the activities, there are art elements, like associating words with pictures, so they can better understand the meaning of the word—not only to read it but also to comprehend it.)

Additionally, the researcher asks Simple (pseudonym) about her technique or strategy in order to make reading more engaging for students who find reading challenging, and she says that in order to address the various needs of the students, she, as a reading coordinator, implements diversified activities, such as games. She believed that students have different needs and want to be taught. She said that:

“You will feed them with differentiated activities not just in reading but mag hatag pud ka ug lahi lahi nga activity for example mga fun activity mga games, ug mga watching movies or videos. Apply more strategy because students has different likes lahi lahi silag gusto, nay uban students gusto mka kitag video naa puy uban gusto sila maminaw naa puy uban nga more on activities, be resourceful apply lang ang mga strategy depende sa capability sa bata.” (IDI-03)

(You will feed them with differentiated activities, not just in reading but also by providing different activities, for example, fun activities, games, and watching movies or videos. Apply more strategy because students have different likes, there are students who like to watch videos, and others just want to listen. Be resourceful and just apply strategies that will depend on the capabilities of the child.)

Moreover, Approachable (pseudonym) mentioned that one of her strategies for scaffolding non-reader pupils involves incorporating enjoyable activities alongside reading exercises. She believes that by making learning fun, students are more likely to engage with the material and stay motivated. This approach not only helps to improve their reading skills but also creates an enjoyable learning experience. She said that:

“Naa man mi Catch Up Friday no, one time is mag activities mi nga prior to reading dili lang gyud nga tutok sa reading, mag activities sa mi mga fun learning activities like that.” (IDI-04)

(We have Catch Up Friday, and one time, we have activities that are prior to reading, not just focused on reading, we have activities first that are fun, fun learning activities like that.)

Lastly, Enthusiastic (pseudonym) explained that she uses games as a way to help non-reader students learn. She believes that making learning fun through games can make reading less intimidating for them. She also lets her students watch videos about reading to keep them interested. To make it even more exciting, she adds a fun challenge while they learn to read. She said that:

“Sometimes I do the gaming, gaming strategy kay ma lingaw pud sila, sometimes I allow them to watch mga clips about sa reading. Naa koy mga pakulo, padula, pa unhanay mao tu na ma motivate sila kay kung kinsay maka una naay reward they will receive something then pasalida about anang reading pod, basa basa gihapun.” (IDI-05)

(Sometimes I do the gaming, gaming strategy allows them to enjoy it, and sometimes I allow them to watch clips about reading. I have something to offer, like games, like a contest where whoever wins has a reward and will receive something, then watching videos about reading, still reading.)

Going Back to the Basics

Letter recognition is the capacity to identify a letter among a group of letters or to recognize and call out a letter that is displayed. Acquiring the skill of letter recognition is essential to learning to read. Children should be able to recognize both the names and sounds of the letters in order to facilitate their learning of reading. Otherwise, learning to read could be challenging for them. For this reason, when teaching non-readers, it is imperative to teach first letter recognition.

Smart (pseudonym) elaborated her approach to scaffolding non-reader students, emphasizing the importance of mastering foundational skills before tackling more complex concepts. She begins by ensuring her students can recognize and understand the letters and sounds of the alphabet, which she believes is crucial for building their confidence and competence in reading. She stated that:

“You must use unified or simplified instruction, you would start from the basic you would start recognizing letters, sounds mas maayu man jud nang makabalo silag basa kaysa tudluan silag lesson kay di man gihapun na musulod sa utok.” (IDI-01)

(Use easy activities, the basics, before proceeding to more complicated ones. You must use unified or simplified instructions. You would start from the basics; you would start recognizing letters and sounds. It is better that they know how to read than teach them lessons because they still cannot comprehend the lessons if they do not know how to read.)

Additionally, Simple (pseudonym) mentioned that she employs going back to basics in teaching non-reader students. Simple (pseudonym) believed that this technique was effective because in teaching non-reader students, the teaching process must be different compared to a normal class. This suggests that instruction with non-readers using a different method and adjusting to the learner’s needs is effective in scaffolding non-readers. She stated that:

“To the students who are non-readers lahi jud ang mga process for example ang ilahang level, mas ginababa man gud namo, as for example, these non-readers naa sila ana na grade level possible ang among ginagamit nga reading material is kadtung mga bigginers katung mga syllable lang mga alphabet recognition and alphabet sound.” (IDI-03)

(To the students who are non-readers, the teaching process is different, for example, we lowered the level as, for example, these non-readers are at that grade level possible we use those reading materials that are for beginners, like starting with the syllable, alphabet recognition, and alphabet sound.)

Moreover, Enthusiastic (pseudonym) also mentioned that many students have a hard time recognizing letters, so she goes back to teaching them phonemic awareness. She focuses on the basics, like helping them understand the sounds that letters make. By starting from the beginning, she helps her non-reading students build a stronger foundation in reading. She said as follows:

“Nibalik man ko, based on my own experience nibalik ko ug phonemic awareness cause they don’t even identify letters so what I did was nibalik kog phonemic awareness and the instructions mother tongue gyud and uttering the words correctly with correct pronunciations ana siya ang nahitabo.” (IDI-05)

(Based on my own experience, I came back to phonemic awareness because they do not even identify letters, so what I did was teach phonemic awareness, and the instructions were in mother tongue, and uttering the words correctly with correct pronunciations that is what happened.)

Utilizing Guided Individual Reading Strategy

One useful method for boosting students' reading skills especially for those who struggle with literacy is to use the Guided Individual Reading Strategy. With the help of a teacher or reading coordinator, kids can receive individualized reading support by being guided through materials that are appropriate for their reading levels. Because this approach is one-on-one, it enables focused instruction that addresses particular difficulties a student may have and builds self-assurance and autonomous reading skills.

When directed by a single person, learners learn most effectively. Smart (pseudonym) scaffolds her non-reader pupils using the guided individual reading strategy. According to her, she used the guided individual reading technique since some kids prefer to learn with just the teacher and themselves, allowing them to learn faster if they are guided by someone. She stated that:

“Not all student wants to learn with other students, naa juy mga bata nga mas gusto nila nga ikaw lang teacher and student lang naay mga in ana, isa na siya sa mga struggle of course dili jud nimu na siya ma force no kay basig mawala pud iyahang interest so dili lang jud nimu siya e mingle sa ubang bata,” (IDI-01)

(Not all students want to learn with other students; there are students who want to learn with only the teacher and student. That is one of the struggles because you cannot force the student because it might affect their interest in learning, that is why you just do not make that student learn with other students.)

Additionally, Simple (pseudonym) also narrated that she utilizes guided individual reading as a technique for scaffolding non-reader students. She mentioned that a one-on-one reading session with the non-reader is effective in scaffolding non-reader students because you give them more time, allowing them to focus on the things that need to be addressed for the learner. She stated that:

“One on one reading, because you can give them more time, ma focusan nimu sila, kung asa ilang need, didtu nimu sila focussan.” (IDI-03)

(One-on-one reading because you can give them more time and you can focus on the things that is need to be addressed.)

Moreover, Enthusiastic (pseudonym) also uses an individual reading strategy to help her non-reader students. She believes that one-on-one reading sessions are the most effective way to teach these students. By working with them individually, she can focus on their specific needs and guide them step by step. This personalized approach has proven to be the best method for helping her non-reader students improve. She said:

“Guided individual reading strategy, guided individual gyud kay kung way mu guide sa ilaha di sila kabasa, as in sila gyud one on one gyud mo, moa ng pinaka effective nga strategy.” (IDI-05)

(A guided individual reading strategy must be guided by the individual because if no one guides them, they will not learn how to read. It is really a one-on-one strategy that is the most effective.)

Employing Peer Tutoring

Reading coordinators utilize peer tutoring to scaffold non-readers, creating a supportive environment for learning. By pairing non-readers with peers of similar age or ability, this approach fosters active learning while reducing embarrassment and isolation. Social interactions promote confidence, community, and responsibility, encouraging non-readers to engage more effectively. Peer tutoring not only improves literacy skills but also nurtures collaboration, helping non-readers feel valued and motivated in their reading journey.

Smart (pseudonym) shared her technique on the most effective way in supporting non-reading students in developing their literacy

skills. She emphasized that collaboration with other readers or independent readers is crucial in this process, as it creates opportunities for learners to share knowledge and learn together. As a reading coordinator, Smart believes that fostering this collaborative environment is key to enhancing students' reading abilities. She stated that:

“You need to collaborate with other reader that is same level, they would share would learn together mugamit ko ug peer tutoring, I ask independent readers to teach them.” (IDI-01)

(You need to collaborate with other readers of the same level, they would share and learn together. Use peer tutoring, I ask independent readers to teach them.)

Additionally, Confident (pseudonym) also finds peer tutoring to be an effective strategy in scaffolding non-reading students, as it helps them develop their literacy skills in a supportive environment. She revealed that, in her role as a reading coordinator, she actively employs this technique by pairing non-readers with students who can read, fostering a collaborative learning experience. Confident ensures that students receive personalized attention and encouragement. She stated that:

“Partnership with those students who can read. Last time we had this peer strategy and technique, such as peer reading, wherein I asked the higher grade level students who are independent readers to teach the non-readers, so they had this 8-week program. I had to facilitate and observe the progress of the students. Those are the methods that have worked for me and are beneficial as well.” (IDI-02)

(Partnering with students who can read. Previously, we implemented a peer strategy, like peer reading, where I asked higher-grade students who are independent readers to teach the non-readers. This was part of an 8-week program, which I facilitated and monitored to observe the students’ progress. These methods have been effective and beneficial for me.)

Moreover, Simple (pseudonym) emphasized the effectiveness of peer tutoring in scaffolding non-reader students, where she facilitates group reading sessions among classmates. This approach helps students feel more comfortable and reduces any shame associated with learning to read, creating a supportive learning environment. Simple ensures that her students receive both academic support and emotional encouragement, making the learning process more effective and inclusive. She stated that:

“Group reading for example sila tanan pabasahon nako kay para dili siya ma ulaw so mag sundog sundog siya sa iyang mga classmate.” (IDI-03)

(Group reading, for example, all of them will read for the non-reader, not be shy, so that non-reader will just imitate their classmates.)

Research Question No. 2: What are the lived experiences of the reading coordinators with non-reader students?

In-depth interviews were conducted with participants to answer the research question. Several sub-questions were asked to uncover the lived experiences of high school reading coordinators in scaffolding non-reader students, focusing on their strategies, challenges, and successes in supporting struggling readers. These interviews provide a understanding of the coordinators' approaches, shedding light on the nuances of their efforts in supporting struggling readers.

From the responses of the reading coordinators, three main challenges emerged as particularly significant. First, the lack of parental involvement was frequently mentioned, as it limits the support students receive at home and hinders their progress. Second, emotional challenges faced by non-reader students, including feelings of shame and embarrassment, which often result in withdrawal or avoidance of participation. Lastly, the coordinators emphasized that students' short attention spans and low retention pose significant challenges, making it difficult for them to stay focused, absorb lessons effectively, and retain information, ultimately hindering their overall literacy growth and development.

Table 3. *Lived Experiences of the reading Coordinators with Non-reader Students*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Observe Lack of Parental Involvement	<p>“Most of these non-readers that we have had in the past and even until now, whenever we ask for support from their parents, we see that there is no parent involved. They cannot assist their children at home in reading because they themselves also have difficulty in reading, so that is the number one most common reason why there are non-readers and struggling readers.”-IDI-02</p> <p>“The barrier that we encounter with the students is at home, lack of attention from the parent, and aside from that, it is hereditary. Once the child is non-reader, there is something from the parent, so most likely, these parents are also non-readers because it is very impossible that the student is in grade 7 or at a higher level but still a non-reader, wherein in the 6 years that they are in school they are more on reading and comprehension, which is very impossible.” -IDI-03</p> <p>“I learned that we need the collaboration of the parents, and if the parent is also a non-reader, they cannot assist their child on how to read, they cannot have a reading remediation at home. But if they cannot teach reading, just at least motivate their child to go to school every day. We really need a partnership with the parents.” -IDI-04</p>
Encounter Students Who Felt Ashamed	<p>“One of the things I noticed is that they are ashamed, as you can see, our reading center is at the end of the school.” -IDI-01</p> <p>“The common barrier is their lack of self-confidence. Because they are already in high school, they feel that they are different from others. They feel ashamed every time we are doing reading remediation, especially when their classmate sees them.” -IDI-04</p>

Dealt with Short Attention Span and Low Retention

“That student is already in Grade 8, and she feels ashamed going back here. I really cannot force her, even though I always tell her, but she would not come back because she feels ashamed.” -IDI-05

“Non-readers also have a short attention span because, at their early age, discipline is not well established.” -IDI-01

“Our struggle is those students who do not have retention, they will read now, then the next day they instantly forget, so another reading session again, then the following day they still forget, they do not have retention, so it is hard to teach if that is the case.” -IDI-03

“Their short period of attention span and then it takes long for them to learn. I will tell them to take vitamins, we are in letter A-D this week, and then next week I will ask them what that letter is, but they already forgot. Also, they have a short attention span, and at the same time, their cognitive process is slow.” -IDI-05

The major themes and core ideas for research question number 2 were presented in Table 3. From the answers of the participants, three major themes emerged: Observe Lack of Parental Involvement, Encounter Students Who Felt Ashamed, and Dealt with Short Attention Span and Low Retention.

Observe Lack of Parental Involvement

A major challenge in scaffolding non-reader students is the lack of parental involvement, which limits reinforcement of reading skills at home. Parents' support is crucial for sustaining literacy progress beyond the classroom. Without it, students face heightened difficulties in learning to read. Effective scaffolding requires collaboration between parents and schools, creating a cohesive support system that fosters consistent practice, encouragement, and a conducive environment for non-readers to develop their reading skills.

Confident (pseudonym) experienced no support from the parents of non-reader students, and it is because they themselves are non-readers. It was revealed that in scaffolding non-reader students, there is a lack of parental involvement that causes the learner to be a non-reader. Confident (pseudonym) states that they always find no parental figures there when they seek non-reader parents for support. She stated that:

“Most of these non-readers that we have had in the past and even until now, whenever we ask for support from their parents, we see that there is no parent involved. They cannot assist their children at home in reading because they themselves also have difficulty in reading, so that's the number one most common reason why there are non-readers and struggling readers.” (IDI-02)

(Most of the non-readers we had, both in the past and even now, have parents who are not involved when we ask for support. They cannot assist their children with reading at home because they also struggle with reading themselves. This is the most common reason why there are non-readers and struggling readers.)

Additionally, Simple (pseudonym) also narrated her experience as a reading coordinator scaffolding non-reader students. She observed a lack of parental involvement in helping the non-reader students. She specifically mentioned that a lack of parental involvement is a barrier to scaffolding non-reader students. Once the child is a non-reader, there is something from the parent. She stated that:

“Barrier nga ma encounter sa bata kay at home, lack of attention from the parent aside ana hereditary, once ang bata dle kabalo mu basa naay something from the parent so most possible kining mga parent is dili pud kabalo mu basa in ana kay its very impossible nga mu abot ang bata sa grade 7 or in higher level nga dili kabalo mu basa wherein sa 6 years nga naa sila sa school more on reading sila and comprehension diba its very impossible.” (IDI-03)

(The barrier that we encounter with the students is at home, lack of attention from the parent, and aside from that, it is hereditary. Once the child is non-reader, there is something from the parent, so most likely, these parents are also non-readers because it's very impossible that the student is in grade 7 or at a higher level but still a non-reader, wherein in the 6 years that they are in school they are more on reading and comprehension, which is very impossible.)

Moreover, during the interview, Approachable (pseudonym) shared her experience in scaffolding non-readers and discussed the significant challenge posed by the lack of parental support. Approachable stressed that fostering a strong partnership between teachers and parents is essential in providing the necessary encouragement and resources for non-readers to succeed. She stated that:

“Na learn nako nga dapat jud naay collaboration sa parents, if ang parent is dle sad kabalo mu basa dle maka tudlo dle maka reading remediate sa ilang anak at least man lang ma motivate nila ilang anak nga mag skwela every day, partnership with parents jud.” (IDI-04)

(I learned that we need the collaboration of the parents, and if the parent is also a non-reader, they cannot assist their child on how to read, they cannot have a reading remediation at home. But if they cannot teach reading, just at least motivate their child to go to school every day. We really need a partnership with the parents.)

Encounter Students Who Felt Ashamed

Scaffolding non-reader students requires addressing their emotional and behavioral challenges tied to reading difficulties. Struggling readers often experience low self-esteem, feeling inferior or ashamed compared to peers, which can negatively impact mental health, causing stress, anxiety, or depression. Their lack of confidence may hinder overall well-being, making emotional support just as crucial as academic strategies. By fostering a positive and encouraging environment, educators can nurture students' self-worth, build

resilience, and support their journey toward literacy development.

Smart (pseudonym) shared that a major barrier faced by non-reader students is the profound sense of embarrassment they often feel. As a reading coordinator, she frequently encounters students whose progress is hindered by shame and self-doubt about their inability to read. This fear of judgment or failure fosters reluctance to participate, creating a frustrating cycle that stalls literacy development. She stated that:

“Isa sa akong nakita is ma ulaw sila, as you can see our reading center is located sa tumoy kilid kaayu.” (IDI-01)

(One of the things I noticed is that they are ashamed, as you can see, our reading center is at the end of the school.)

Additionally, Approachable (pseudonym) also shared that her non-reader students often feel ashamed during reading remediation sessions. She noted that this shame can severely undermine their self-confidence, making it even more challenging to engage them in the learning process. Self-esteem of these students is critical, as their lack of confidence becomes a significant barrier in supporting their reading development. She stated that:

“Common nga barrier jud is ilahang lack of self-confidence kana gung high school na man gud sila ma ulaw na sila, therefore feel nila lahi sila sa uban, lahi sila sa kasagaran so murag ma ulaw sila inig everytime mag reading remiadiation mi especially if makakita ilahang mga classmate” (IDI-O4)

(The common barrier is their lack of self-confidence. Because they are already in high school, they feel that they are different from others. They feel ashamed every time we are doing reading remediation, especially when their classmate sees them.)

Moreover, Enthusiastic (pseudonym) shared that some students feel too embarrassed about not being able to read, so they stop coming to their reading sessions. She explained that, despite her efforts to encourage the student, she cannot force them to return. Even though she reassures the student, their shame about being a non-reader keeps them from not coming back. She said as follows:

“Grade 8 na mn siya run ma ulaw na siya mu balik dre, d kaayu nko ma force bisag sige nakog ingnon di na man mu balik kay ma ulaw.” (IDI-05)

(That student is already in Grade 8, and she feels ashamed going back here. I really cannot force her, even though I always tell her, but she would not come back because she feels ashamed.)

Dealt with Short Attention Span and Low Retention

A short attention span may make it challenging for a person to focus on a task for a long time without becoming easily distracted. Everyone has occasional mental lapses, and certain situations could make it harder to focus and pay attention. When learning to read, a student's comprehension and recollection of the content may suffer because of their short attention span. It is possible that they will struggle to focus on the text, which will hinder their ability to process the information and slow down the development of their reading skills.

Smart (pseudonym) shares that the reason there are students who are not readers is because they struggle with memory retention and attention deficit problems. When scaffolding non-reader students, the reading coordinator stated that they were dealing with pupils who had poor recall and a short attention span, and it was giving them a hard time teaching them how to read. She stated that:

“They have also short attention span kasi sa ilahang early age wala kaau na establish ang discipline, wala kaayu because lack of assistance.” (IDI-01)

(Non-readers also have a short attention span because, at their early age, discipline is not well established because lack of assistance.)

Additionally, Simple (pseudonym) highlighted that one of the significant challenges she faces in scaffolding non-reader students is dealing with their short attention spans and low retention of information. These cognitive barriers make it difficult for students to stay focused during lessons and absorb the material effectively. Simple emphasized that the combination of limited attention and difficulty retaining information complicates the scaffolding process. She stated that:

“Our struggle is mga bata nga walay retention pabasahon nimu sila karun then the next day makalimot na sad sila so another session na pud of reading then the following day makalimot na sad sila because wala silay retention so lisod sila tudluan pag in ana.” (IDI-03)

(Our struggle is those students who do not have retention, they will read now, then the next day they instantly forget, so another reading session again, then the following day they still forget, they do not have retention, so it is hard to teach if that is the case.)

Moreover, Enthusiastic (pseudonym) also mentioned that many non-reader students struggle to retain the lessons she teaches. She explained that these students often have short attention spans, making it hard for them to stay focused during reading activities. Additionally, their cognitive processing is slower, so it takes them longer to grasp reading concepts. These challenges make it more difficult for them to make steady progress in learning to read. She stated that:

“Kadtu short period of attention span and then dugay masulod sa ilang utok gyud , magbalik na mi lang A-D nami karun na simana

pagka sunod nga simana unsa ni nga letter nalimtan na pud kadtu siya ang span sa ilang attention is gamay at the same time ang cognitive process nila dili musulod sa ilang utok ilag gi estadihan.“ (IDI-05)

(Their short period of attention span and then it takes long for them to learn. I will tell them to take vitamins, we are in letter A-D this week, and then next week I will ask them what that letter is, but they already forgot. Also, they have a short attention span, and at the same time, their cognitive process is slow.)

Research Question No. 3: What coping mechanisms do they employ to deal with the issues of scaffolding non-readers?

To answer this research question, in-depth interviews were conducted with the participants. To learn how reading coordinators cope with the challenges of dealing with non-reader students, a number of questions were posed. The emerging theme was prioritizing reading remediation, considering student’s background and situations, using reward system, and being passionate about one’s job.

From the participants' responses, four major themes became clear. First, is the significance of prioritizing reading remediation. The participants emphasized the need to focus on building strong reading skills. They recognized that without proper reading remediation, these students would continue to face challenges in their academic journey. Additionally, participants highlighted the importance of considering students' backgrounds and situations of the students. Understanding each student's unique circumstances, including their home environment, prior educational experiences, and personal challenges, was essential in designing and delivering tailored support that effectively addressed their individual learning needs and goals.

Another key theme in scaffolding non-reader students was the effective use of a reward system. Participants noted that tangible rewards, such as praise, stickers, or small prizes, had a profound impact on boosting students' motivation and reinforcing positive behaviors. These incentives not only helped maintain students' engagement but also fostered a sense of accomplishment, encouraging them to persist in their reading progress. Additionally, the importance of passion in teaching was emphasized by educators, who highlighted that genuine enthusiasm for students' success is vital in creating a positive, supportive environment. A teacher’s passion can significantly enhance students' motivation, making the learning process more enjoyable and rewarding.

Table 4. Coping Mechanisms that Reading Coordinator Employ

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Prioritizing Reading Remediation	<p>“Adjustment on my own schedule, because I am a fully loaded teacher, I teach 6–8 subjects in a week, and I am also a research teacher, and plus this one, I am a reading coordinator, so what I have to do is sacrifice my hours of paper work, I have to adjust it, make sure that I can accommodate them, my paper work I have to bring them at home cause I cannot bring the students home, so the students should be here and my paper work I bring it at home, so that is how I made the adjustment, just like teachers bring their work at home because even during our vacant time we have to accommodate these students.” -IDI-02</p> <p>“There are adjustments. Of course, in a day we have 5 loads, then we have 3 vacant loads, so instead of making paper works, we use that time to teach the students how to read. It is not easy because you are giving your free time for the students to learn how to read. Instead of taking a break or doing something, that is why there is an adjustment.” -IDI-03</p> <p>I am full of work load because we have a short vacant time just one hour then we need to make a PowerPoint presentation, so what must we prioritize? Making power points or having a reading remediation. Sometimes, for me to have time for reading remediation in my vacant time, I am already making the power point at home. I.” -IDI-04</p>
Considering Student’s Background and Situations	<p>“When I handle non-reader students, I understand the different situations of students and how they become like that, so I need to adjust my strategy.” -IDI-01</p> <p>“The first thing that we need to consider in addressing the needs of these non-reading students is that we need to make sure that the strategy that is selected for them is also suited or appropriate to their reading needs because there are many diverse needs and situations.” -IDI-02</p> <p>“Of course, before you give a remediation, you will talk to the students first for you to know their background. It is important to know their background, like if the parents know how to read, if they have electricity, and their way of life. Because it is a factor like the electricity, how can they practice reading if they do not have a source of light or instead of having time to read, they are busy finding work to help their family? That is why it is important to background check.” -IDI-03</p>
Using Reward System	<p>“The reward system, "If you can read, I will give you ballpen, read all the 50 words here, and if you have one mistake, I will take one of the candy.” Most struggling readers are in grade 7, and grade 7 is still young still kids.” -IDI-01</p> <p>“I manage to cope by making sure that they are given something to look forward to, for example, “do not be absent tomorrow because I will be giving rewards to those who will complete the activity and then plus points to your other subjects.” So that is how I cope; the reward system is something that is still useful and effective as of this day.” -IDI-02</p> <p>“In reading sessions, they will tend to be bored, and they will not listen to you anymore, so I have tricks and games. For them to be motivated is we have a reward system in which they will receive something,” -IDI-04</p>
Being Passionate about One’s Job	<p>“Sympathy for the students is also a factor, because your teaching is different if you do not have a heart for children; it is just plain teaching, while if you have a heart for the children, your teaching is different because you will work hard for them to learn how to read.” -IDI-03</p> <p>“The students are our obligations, it is our duty, it is our responsibility, and we are accountable if they do not know</p>

how to read because we are a reading teacher, so we need to have a reading remediation for them.” -IDI-04
“I just manage it well because I love teaching them reading, it is my passion. I am so happy doing this every day. I am so glad in every progress that I encounter with the students, and I am happy upon doing all of those things.” -IDI-05

The major themes and core ideas for research question number 3 were presented in Table 4. From the answers of the participants, four major themes emerged: Prioritizing Reading Remediation, Considering Student’s Background and Situations, Using Reward System, and Being Passionate about One’s Job.

Prioritizing Reading Remediation

Reading coordinators prioritize scaffolding non-reader students by focusing heavily on reading remediation, recognizing its crucial role in boosting confidence and academic success. Addressing reading challenges early can greatly influence a student's overall performance and future opportunities. Coordinators often set aside other responsibilities to ensure struggling readers receive targeted support and interventions. By dedicating resources and attention to remediation, they create an environment where non-readers can thrive, fostering both their academic growth and personal development with lasting impact.

Confident (pseudonym) shares that to overcome all the challenges as a reading coordinator is to consider prioritizing reading remediation for her students as a coping mechanism in dealing with the issues of scaffolding non-reader students. It was rendered clear during the in-depth interview that Confident disclosed that, as a teacher scaffolding non-reader student, you will give reading remediation first priority and that the paperwork will be brought home. She stated that:

“Adjustment on my own schedule, because I am a fully loaded teacher, I teach 6–8 subjects in a week, and I’m also a research teacher, and plus this one, I am a reading coordinator, so what I have to do is sacrifice my hours of paper work, I have to adjust it, make sure that I can accommodate them, my paper work I have to bring them at home cause I cannot bring the students home, so the students should be here and my paper work I bring it at home, so that’s how I made the adjustment, just like teachers bring their work at home because even during our vacant time we have to accommodate these students.” (IDI-02)

(I have to adjust my own schedule because I am a fully loaded teacher, teaching 6 to 8 subjects a week. I am also a research teacher and a reading coordinator. To manage everything, I sacrifice my paperwork hours; I have to adjust and ensure I can accommodate the students. I bring my paperwork home since I cannot take the students with me. The students need to be here, and my paperwork goes home with me. That is how I make these adjustments—just like other teachers who bring work home because even during our free time, we need to accommodate these students.)

Additionally, Simple (pseudonym) also stated that she needs to make adjustments in her schedule to allocate more time for her non-reader students, emphasizing the importance of reading remediation. Simple mentioned that in focusing on helping these students improve their reading skills, she prioritizes reading remediation during her free time, even over completing paperwork. She stated that:

“Naa juy adjustment kay of course no sa isa ka adlaw we have 5 loads then we have 3 vacant loads so instead of making paper works gina gamit namo siya to teach the students on how to read dili siya lalim kay ginahatag nimu imohang free time para sa mga bata nga di kabalo mu basa instead of pwede ka makapahulay pwede ka makahimu ug lain nga activity, so naa jud siyay adjustment.” (IDI-03)

(There are adjustments. Of course, in a day we have 5 loads, then we have 3 vacant loads, so instead of making paper works, we use that time to teach the students how to read. It is not easy because you are giving your free time for the students to learn how to read. Instead of taking a break or doing something, that is why there is an adjustment.)

Moreover, Approachable (pseudonym) expressed that her workload is overwhelming. Despite the demands, she prioritizes reading remediation over tasks like creating PowerPoints, recognizing the immediate impact that literacy support has on her students. Approachable emphasized that while other tasks are important, helping non-readers develop their skills takes precedence because it directly influences their academic success. She stated that:

“I am full work load kay kani laging gamay na lang atuang vacant time isa aka oras lang unya mu himu pa tag power point so unsa man atung unahaon ang power point nga e tudlo natu or ang pag remadiate. Usahay para ma free ko, para wala nakoy himuon sa akoang vacant time para mag remadiate na lang jud ko is sa balay naga himu nako daan ug powerpoint.” (IDI-04)

(I am full of work load because we have a short vacant time just one hour then we need to make a PowerPoint presentation, so what must we prioritize? Making power points or having a reading remediation. Sometimes, for me to have time for reading remediation in my vacant time, I am already making the power point at home.)

Considering the student’s background and situation

Understanding each student's background and particular conditions is crucial while teaching non-readers. There are pupils whose parents are too busy or lack the time to assist them with reading, or who come from households with limited resources. Language obstacles, learning difficulties, or poverty could be obstacles that others must overcome. Teachers can modify their pedagogy to suit the unique needs of each student by being aware of these variables. Understanding the background of a student aids educators in

establishing a nurturing classroom that takes into account their particular needs.

Smart (pseudonym) shares that she used to overcome all the challenges as a reading coordinator by considering the student's background and situations because it is a factor in understanding why the student doesn't know how to read and what makes them have difficulty learning to read. Teachers can better fulfill the needs of the students based on their awareness of the students' backgrounds. She said that:

“When I handle non-reader students, I understand the different situations of students and how they become like that, so I need to adjust my strategy.” (IDI-01)

(When I work with non-reader students, I take into account their various circumstances and the reasons behind their struggles, so can adjust my teaching strategies accordingly.)

Additionally, Confident (pseudonym) believed that we have diverse kinds of students who come from different environments and have different needs. She stated that because each individual has particular situations, she takes individual characteristics into account while scaffolding non-readers so that the scaffolding technique is suitable to the learner's needs. She stated that:

“The first thing that we need to consider in addressing the needs of these non-reading students is that we need to make sure that the strategy that is selected for them is also suited to or appropriate to their reading needs because there are many diverse needs and situations.” (IDI-02)

(The first thing we need to consider in addressing the needs of non-reading students is ensuring that the strategy we select for them is suited to or appropriate for their reading needs, as there are many diverse needs and situations.)

Moreover, Simple (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of evaluating her students' backgrounds. She believes that understanding the unique situations and challenges faced by each student is crucial for providing effective support. As a reading coordinator, she stresses that knowing a student's background enables her to tailor her approach and offer the most appropriate help. She stated that:

“Syempre before you will give a remediation you will talk to the students para maka balo ka sa ilang background, importante man gud kung kabalo ka ilang background like iyang mama ug papa ba kabalo mu basa , sa ilang balay naa bay suga kung unsa ba sila ka pobrehon kay factor man pd gud ni siya kay kung in ana wala silay suga sa balay how they will practice reading or instead of having time to read mangita na lang kag panginabuhi kay para maka tabang ka sa pamlya so kinahanglan nimu siya e background check.” (IDI-03)

(Of course, before you give a remediation, you will talk to the students first for you to know their background. It is important to know their background, like if the parents know how to read, if they have electricity, and their way of life. Because it is a factor like the electricity, how can they practice reading if they do not have a source of light or instead of having time to read, they are busy finding work to help their family? That is why it is important to background check.)

Using Reward System

One of the best ways to encourage pupils who are not readers to pick up reading is by using a reward system. Students are motivated to keep trying when they receive small rewards for their efforts, such as stickers, recognition, or additional time off. Learning becomes enjoyable and their confidence is strengthened by this positive reinforcement. Even little improvement can be motivating for non-readers who may struggle or feel behind if there is a reward system in place. Students are more likely to participate and advance their skills when reading is made to feel more pleasurable and rewarding.

At this point, Smart (pseudonym) shared that the reward system is what she uses to cope with the challenges in scaffolding non-reader. She stated that in her class, she gives her students a reward if they accomplish something, and in that way, the students will be motivated to learn in her class because she believes that students in secondary school are still kids. She said that:

“The reward system “ug makabasa ka tagaan takag ballpen, mabasa gani nimu ni tanan dire kaning 50 words unya kung mamali kag isa kuhaan natu imong candy” mostly sa struggling readers is grade 7 and grade 7 is still young still kids.” (IDI-01)

(The reward system, "If you can read, I will give you ballpen, read all the 50 words here, and if you have one mistake, I'll take one of the candy." Most struggling readers are in grade 7, and grade 7 is still young still kids.)

Additionally, Confident (pseudonym) shared that in coping with the issues of scaffolding non-readers, she utilizes a reward system in teaching her non-readers. She stated that she manages to cope by making sure that the students are given something to look forward to in attending classes with her; in that way, her students will attend and be motivated to learn with her in their reading sessions. She stated that:

“I manage to cope by making sure that they are given something to look forward to, for example, “do not be absent tomorrow because I'll be giving rewards to those who will complete the activity and then plus points to your other subjects.” So that's how I cope; the reward system is something that is still useful and effective as of this day.” (IDI-02)

(I manage to cope by ensuring that they have something to look forward to. For example, I tell them, ‘Do not be absent tomorrow

because I will be giving rewards to those who complete the activity, plus points for your other subjects.’ That is how I cope; the reward system is still useful and effective to this day.)

Moreover, Approachable (pseudonym) believes that offering rewards is an effective strategy to combat student boredom and keep them engaged in the classroom. She observed that many students easily lose interest during lessons, so she incorporates rewards as a way to reignite their motivation and encourage active participation. She said as follows:

“Pag mag pabasa they will tend to be bored, bored na sila and they will not listen to you anymore so mao tu naa koy mga pakulo, padula , pa unhanay mao tu na ma motivate sila kay kung kinsay maka una naay reward they will receive something then pasalida about anang reading pod , basa basa gihapun.” (IDI-04)

(In reading sessions, they will tend to be bored, and they will not listen to you anymore, so I have tricks and games. For them to be motivated is we have a reward system in which they will receive something.)

Being Passionate about One’s Job

Reading coordinators have to be really passionate about what they do in order to tackle the difficulties of scaffolding non-readers. An educator's commitment to their students' achievement is what makes them distinct. For teaching to be successful, commitment is essential. Since they are concerned about their students' personal development, committed educators deal greatly with how to support their learning. Teachers that are enthusiastic about their work and committed to supporting students' learning considerably contribute to the progress of their students.

Simple (pseudonym) expressed a profound love for her work, viewing it as a vital foundation for overcoming the challenges of supporting non-reader children. She emphasized that teaching extends far beyond delivering lessons; it requires genuine care, empathy, and an unwavering commitment to the well-being of each student. For her, having a compassionate heart and building meaningful connections with the children is not just important—it’s indispensable. She firmly believes that:

“Factor pud nang naa kay kaluoy sa mga bata kay lahi man pud nang mag tudlo ka nga wala kay heart sa mga bata just plain teaching while kung naa kay heart para sa mga bata lahi imong tinudluan kay maningkamot ka unsaon pagpabasa sa ilaha.” (IDI-03)

(Sympathy for the students is also a factor, because your teaching is different if you do not have a heart for children; it is just plain teaching, while if you have a heart for the children, your teaching is different because you will work hard for them to learn how to read.)

Additionally, Approachable (pseudonym) emphasized that reading coordinators play a crucial role in ensuring non-readers receive the necessary scaffolding and support as they work to develop their reading skills. Additionally, Approachable highlighted that teachers are ultimately accountable for their students' reading abilities, making it essential for them to actively engage in and support each learner's progress. She stated that:

“Atuang obligasyon ang mga estudyante it is our duty, it is our responsibility ug tulubagon nату kung dle sila makabasa kay reading teacher man ta so atua sila dapat e remediate.” (IDI-04)

(The students are our obligations, it is our duty, it is our responsibility, and we are accountable if they do not know how to read because we are a reading teacher, so we need to have a reading remediation for them.)

Moreover, Enthusiastic (pseudonym) shared that she has a deep passion for teaching non-readers and genuinely enjoys helping them learn to read. Her love for teaching drives her to overcome the many challenges that come with supporting non-reader students. Because she truly loves what she does, she finds joy in managing the difficulties and seeing her students make progress. She said as follows:

“I just manage it well because I love teaching them reading, it’s my passion. I am so happy doing this every day. I’m so glad in every progress that I encounter with the students, and I am happy upon doing all of those things.” (IDI-05)

(I just manage it well because I love teaching them reading—it’s my passion. I am so happy doing this every day. I am glad with every bit of progress I see in the students, and I feel happy doing all of these things.)

Research Question No. 4: What are the insights of reading coordinators on scaffolding students who are non-readers?

To address this research question, in-depth interviews were conducted with the participants to gather comprehensive insights. The interview process involved several sub-questions designed to explore the specific experiences and perspectives of reading coordinators on scaffolding non-reader students. The responses were meticulously analyzed by the researcher, and the major themes and core ideas that emerged from the answer of the participants were systematically organized and presented in Table 5. The researcher carefully examined the responses, uncovering a rich tapestry of valuable insights intricately woven from the diverse experiences shared by the participants.

The major themes and core ideas for research question number 4 were presented in Table 5. From the answers of the participants, five major themes emerged: Give Emphasis on the Foundation, Demonstrate Unwavering Patience, Give More Focus on Reading, Embrace Individual Differences, and Gain a Sense of Fulfilment.

Table 5. *Insights of Reading Coordinators on Scaffolding Students who are Non-readers*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Give Emphasis on the Foundation	<p>“They are not actually able to read because the foundation that they have at an early age is not actually funded, it is not established. From elementary school on, it must be the foundation for reading because it is hard when they are already in high school. Why not DepEd focus on numeracy and literacy in elementary and not let them proceed to the next level if they do not master the skills that they need to master in that particular level.” -IDI-01</p> <p>“The foundation of the students must be strong, so when we say foundation, it is in elementary school, so children should focus on reading in elementary school because it will be difficult if they graduate without knowing how to read, it will be difficult to teach in high school. Yes, we can train them in high school, but the impact on them is not that much, better if when they were still in elementary school they were already assessed so that, as early as possible, we could see their reading efficiency.” -IDI-03</p> <p>“It is better if I teach elementary students, or those who are beginning readers, rather than high school level students, and besides, it really must be in elementary where they learn reading.” -IDI-04</p>
Demonstrate Unwavering Patience	<p>“We need to be patient. Be very patient because your problem is the child itself.” -IDI-01</p> <p>“More patient, and you need to think beyond the box for them to know how to read.” -IDI-03</p> <p>“Let us be patient in dealing with them and keep in mind that they are our responsibility. It is not easy, and sometimes it is better to teach elementary students or those who are beginners in learning reading than to teach students who are in high school because we sometimes hit their interest and self-confidence. That is why sometimes they are not willing to learn. That is why it is not easy.” -IDI-04</p>
Give More Focus on Reading	<p>“Focus on reading without any other subjects, because even if there are subjects, it is still useless because how could they comprehend inside the classroom if they do not know how to read? That is why they must focus on reading first.” -IDI-03</p> <p>“Teachers will focus on reading remediation, which is what we need here in high school.” -IDI-04</p> <p>“Give time one-on-one for guided reading; spend time one-on-one for guided reading because if you blend them with students who know how to read, there is no progress. You must give your students time to have a one-on-one reading.” -IDI-05</p>
Embrace Individual Differences	<p>“There are non-readers who just need one-on-one instruction; there are others who need instruction with the group; for example, they needed to be given a task as a group so that they would learn from others as well; and then there are also non-readers who lack memorization; they have difficulty in their memory; there are also others who have difficulty identifying the words and the sounds; so we have to make sure that each of the instructions given to them in terms of the approach is appropriate, making sure that their needs are addressed.” -IDI-02</p> <p>“We need to accept with an open mind that not every student is blessed with the ability to read because we have less fortunate students, and they are our obligation and responsibility, so let us do our part.” -IDI-04</p> <p>“Sometimes we wonder what this kind of student is, but we cannot force them. I have that kind of principle: consider individual differences; everyone's brain processes differently.” -IDI-05</p>
Gain a Sense of Fulfilment	<p>“I am very happy. Last time my student and I had a class here, my co-teachers were amazed because that student could already read. It is very fulfilling because you see not just my hard work but also the hard work of my co-teachers. It is actually a success, if they can read even just 2-3 words, it is a great improvement.” -IDI-01</p> <p>“I had this student very close to me during the reading remediation, and actually this student has an intellectual disability (ID). He really can only retain information for a shorter time, but there was an instance where I asked him to do a task and was able to execute it. That was the time that I realized that although he cannot read everything that a student at his level can read, he was able to successfully comprehend the most basic words, so that is how I felt that I was successful during that time.” -IDI-02</p> <p>“Just like my student before she is a girl, at first she does not really know how to read, so I focus on that student because we are applying one-on-one reading intervention, so at first I apply sounds, so after almost a year she is still a non-reader. The following year, we already blended sound. I am a bit happy at that time because at least she can blend sounds, so the following year we are still blending, and then the third year we proceed to syllables, so there are changes from non-reader to struggling reader.” -IDI-03</p> <p>“There was a time last year I focused on that one student, she is a girl. At first, I noticed that she really did not know the sounds of the letters, but because I focused on her at least once a week, we saw each other, and I noticed that she had a willingness to learn how to read, and at the end of the school year, though she could not utter the words properly, she could already read, she is not a non-reader anymore.” -IDI-04</p> <p>“I am so proud of myself, out of 24 non-readers, there is only one student who remains a non-reader. I am so proud of myself because I contributed a lot to their future. I was wondering before if I could do it, but I manage everything.” -IDI-05</p>

Give Emphasis on the Foundation

More than merely a necessary subject in primary school, reading is the foundation on which developing readers build critical thinking skills that will serve them well in their future endeavors. Without strong reading abilities, students frequently find it difficult to keep up with the academic program in high school, which can have an impact on their self-confidence and academic performance. Thus, ensuring that children are ready for more advanced study in high school and beyond begins with helping them develop excellent reading skills in elementary school. The instruction of reading in primary school eventually lays the groundwork for a lifetime of learning and growth.

Smart (pseudonym) shared that some students remain non-readers because the foundational reading skills they were supposed to acquire at an early age were not adequately nurtured. Smart firmly believes that a strong reading foundation must be established at the elementary level to ensure students are prepared for the more complex literacy demands of secondary education. She stated that:

“They are not actually can read because the foundation that they have in early age is not actually funded dili siya establish. From elementary dapat mao jud na siyay foundation sa reading, lisod na man gud sa highschool, why not DepEd would focus on numeracy and literacy in elementary and not let them proceed to the next level if they do not master the skills that they need to master in that particular level.” (IDI-01)

(They are not actually able to read because the foundation that they have at an early age is not actually funded, it is not established. From elementary school on, it must be the foundation for reading because it is hard when they are already in high school. Why not DepEd focus on numeracy and literacy in elementary and not let them proceed to the next level if they do not master the skills that they need to master in that particular level.)

Additionally, Simple (pseudonym) emphasized the significant role of focusing on the foundation of reading. She noted that students should learn to read in elementary school because it becomes challenging to teach them in high school if they graduate without this fundamental skill. She also believed that students should be assessed while they are still in elementary school. She stated that:

“Dapat ang ilahang foundation is strong so when we say foundation naa na siya sa elementary so dapat sa elementary pa lang e focus na sa mga bata ang reading kay kung mu graduate sila sa elementary nga dili kabasa lisod na para sa amoa dire nga mupabasa sa ilaha kay maglisod name, lisod na e train ang bata pag naa na dire although ma train namo pero dili na in ana ka kadako ang impact so dapat pag naa pa lang sa elementary dapat e assess na ang mga bata didtu sa elementary para as early as possible dapat ma assess na ang bata kay para kung makita nga naa nay reading efficiency.” (IDI-03)

(The foundation of the students must be strong, so when we say foundation, it is in elementary school, so children should focus on reading in elementary school because it will be difficult if they graduate without knowing how to read, it will be difficult to teach in high school. Yes, we can train them in high school, but the impact on them is not that much, better if when they were still in elementary school they were already assessed so that, as early as possible, we could see their reading efficiency.)

Moreover, Approachable (pseudonym) expressed that teaching reading at the secondary level is particularly challenging, as students at this stage often struggle with foundational skills they should have acquired earlier. She emphasized the importance of students learning to read in elementary school, where there is more time to build these essential skills. She stated that:

“Mas maayu pa nga elementary nga bata or beginning readers akong tudluan kaysa sa kaning ni abot nag high school, ug sa elementary mn jud dapat na sila maka balo ug basa.” (IDI-04)

(It is better if I teach elementary students, or those who are beginning readers, rather than high school level students, and besides, it really must be in elementary where they learn reading.)

Demonstrate Unwavering Patience

The learning process may at times be frustrating for both the student and the teacher, and it takes consistent repetition and encouragement for them to get better. Being patient fosters a good, encouraging environment where students feel free to make errors and pursue their own learning goals. Teachers can provide non-readers with the consistent direction they need to finally improve their reading abilities if they are patient with them.

Smart (pseudonym) emphasized that scaffolding non-reader students requires a reading coordinator to demonstrate unwavering patience. Smart explained and highlighted that understanding and addressing these deeper issues is crucial, as the problem often stems from the student’s struggles rather than the content itself. She stated that:

“Be patient, mag baon ka talaga nang maraming pasensiya kay ang problema man gyud nimu ana no is the bata gyud.” (IDI-01)

(We need to be patient. Be very patient because your problem is the child itself.)

Additionally, Simple (pseudonym), becoming a reading coordinator demands a great deal of patience, as it involves working closely with students who struggle with reading. She emphasized the importance of thinking beyond the box, meaning that to effectively support non-reader students, one must develop creative and unconventional strategies that go beyond standard teaching methods. She said as follows:

“More patient, dapat mu think kag beyond the box kay para makabalo sila mu basa.” (IDI-03)

(More patient, and you need to think beyond the box for them to know how to read.)

Moreover, Approachable (pseudonym) highlighted that scaffolding non-reader pupils requires immense patience, as their progress is often gradual and the obstacles they face can be multifaceted. She stressed that supporting non-readers is a demanding task that goes beyond routine teaching, necessitating unwavering dedication and consistent effort. Approachable believes that helping these students is responsibility and a testament to the commitment of an educator. She stated that:

“Let’s be patient in dealing with them and let’s bear in mind that they are our responsibility. Dle lalim usahay maka ingun ko nga mas maayu pa nga elementary nga bata or beginning readers akong tudluan kaysa sa kaning ni abot nag high school kay ilaha man gung interest usahay ang atuang mahit ilahang self-confidence mao nang usahay dle sila willing so I think dle jud siya lalim.” (IDI-04)

(Let us be patient in dealing with them and keep in mind that they are our responsibility. It is not easy, and sometimes it is better to teach elementary students or those who are beginners in learning reading than to teach students who are in high school because we sometimes hit their interest and self-confidence. That is why sometimes they are not willing to learn. That is why it is not easy.)

Give More Focus on Reading

Reading is a basic yet significant part of being human since it enables us to find and share knowledge, especially for students. Reading should be prioritized more since it fosters children's intellectual and personal development. Learning resources are always available, particularly books. Not only is reading a good habit, but it's also highly important. Reading sharpens focus, enhances memory, helps with language development.

Simple (pseudonym) believed that placing a greater emphasis on reading was crucial to effectively supporting non-reader students. She suggested that in order to help these students improve more quickly, the focus should be exclusively on reading, without the distraction of other subjects. By concentrating solely on reading, Simple felt that students would be able to develop their skills more rapidly and confidently. She stated that:

“Focus on reading, reading without any other subjects kay nganu kung naay subjects its really useless gihapun kay unsaon nila pag sabot kung dili sila kabalo mu basa unsaon nila pagsabot dihaa sa sulod sa room a lain subject, so dapat reading sila magsugod.” (IDI-03)

(Focus on reading without any other subjects, because even if there are subjects, it is still useless because how could they comprehend inside the classroom if they do not know how to read? That is why they must focus on reading first.)

Additionally, Approachable (pseudonym) believed that teachers should prioritize reading remediation because it addresses need of their students—developing essential literacy skills. She believes teachers need to focus more on reading. Approachable emphasized that reading is foundational to academic success, and therefore, it should be given precedence over other activities in the classroom. She stated that:

“Mas maayu pa nga elementary nga bata or beginning mao na amoang kinahanglan sa pagka karun sa high school.” (IDI-04)

(Teachers will focus on reading remediation, which is what we need here in high school.)

Moreover, Enthusiastic (pseudonym) emphasized that reading coordinators should spend more time focusing on non-readers individually, as blending them with students who can already read hinders their progress. She believes that one-on-one reading sessions are essential for helping these students catch up and improve their skills. She stated that:

“Give time one on one a guided reading, spend time one on one in a guided reading kay kung e halo nimu na siya dha sa kabalo na mu basa wa jud nay pprogress tagaan jug time nga siya lang one on one siya.” (IDI-05)

(Give time one-on-one for guided reading; spend time one-on-one for guided reading because if you blend them with students who know how to read, there is no progress. You must give your students time to have a one-on-one reading.)

Embrace Individual Differences

A vast array of characteristics, including learning preferences, character qualities, cognitive abilities, and sociocultural backgrounds, are examples of individual differences. These differences influence how people perceive, process, and respond to information, leading to a range of learning outcomes even when tutoring non-reader kids. Teachers must recognize and take into consideration these individual characteristics in order to successfully improve education and nurture the most effective learning experiences for each student.

Confident (pseudonym) shared that she, as a reading coordinator, felt that since every student is distinctive, it is important to take their differences into account. Confident shared that in scaffolding non-reader students, they need to consider individualized student traits for her to know the appropriate method to employ in teaching her non-reader students. In that way, she can tailor her teaching techniques to the student’s needs. She stated that:

“There are non-readers who just need one-on-one instruction; there are others who need instruction with the group; for example, they needed to be given a task as a group so that they would learn from others as well; and then there are also non-readers who lack memorization; they have difficulty in their memory; there are also others who have difficulty identifying the words and the sounds; so we have to make sure that each of the instructions given to them in terms of the approach is appropriate, making sure that their needs are addressed.” (IDI-02)

(Reading coordinators consider each student's background and circumstances when working with non-reader students. By understanding the different factors that contribute to their reading challenges, they can adjust their teaching strategies to meet individual

needs effectively. This approach ensures that instruction is relevant and supportive, creating a more inclusive and effective learning environment.)

Additionally, Approachable (pseudonym) believes that every child has different abilities it's important to consider this when helping them. She emphasized the need to approach each student with an open mind, recognizing that not all students are naturally good at reading. Approachable pointed out that some students come from less fortunate backgrounds, which can affect their ability to read, so it's crucial to be understanding and supportive in addressing their needs. She stated that:

“Dawat dawat pero with an open heart with an open mind let's just accept nga dle jud tanan estudyante blessed with the ability to read na dayun kay naa juy mga disadvantage students mga less fortunate students so atua na silang obligasyon, atua na silang responsibilidad so let's do our part na lang , d na mag kwenta.” (IDI-04)

(We need to accept with an open mind that not every student is blessed with the ability to read because we have less fortunate students, and they are our obligation and responsibility, so let us do our part.)

Moreover, Enthusiastic (pseudonym) also strongly believes that it's important to recognize and respect individual differences in students, especially when teaching non-readers. She understands that each student's brain works differently, and this affects how they learn to read. By considering these unique learning styles and needs, she tables to help her non-reader students. She stated that:

“Sometimes naay mga time nga kana ganing ma kuan naka unsa man ning bataa ni pero di biya natu ma pugos naa man ko ana nga principles consider individual differences lahi lahi gyud tag utok sa process.” (IDI-05)

(Sometimes we wonder what this kind of student is, but we cannot force them. I have that kind of principle: consider individual differences; everyone's brain processes differently.)

Gain a Sense of Fulfilment

Scaffolding non-reader students highlights the challenges and dedication inherent in teaching. Supporting struggling readers can be demanding and exhausting, requiring experience and persistence. However, educators find fulfillment in leading by example, inspiring their students, and helping them unlock their potential. Despite daily obstacles, teachers remain passionate about their role, driven by a love for what they do and a commitment to shaping a brighter future for the next generation through patience, perseverance, and genuine care.

Smart (pseudonym) shared that after successfully teaching non-reader students, she experiences a deep sense of fulfillment. She recounted a particular instance where she was able to make a significant impact on a non-reader, transforming their reading abilities and confidence. For her, the greatest joy comes from witnessing the progress of her students She stated that:

“I am very happy, last time katung student nako last year kay dre mi nag klase na amaze akoang mga co-teachers kay makabasa na siya. It is very fulfilling kay nakita nimu imong hard work dle lang na saakoa pati sa akoang mga kauban its actually a success, maka basa lang na silag 2-3 words lami na kaau na it's a great improvement.” (IDI-01)

(I am very happy. Last time my student and I had a class here, my co-teachers were amazed because that student could already read. It is very fulfilling because you see not just my hard work but also the hard work of my co-teachers. It is actually a success, if they can read even just 2-3 words, it is a great improvement.)

Also, Confident (pseudonym) expressed that she found great fulfillment in teaching non-reader students, especially when witnessing their growth and improvement. She recounted a specific instance where her efforts made a significant impact on a non-reader, resulting in noticeable progress. This experience deeply resonated with her, reinforcing her passion and commitment to helping these students succeed. She stated that:

“I had this student very close to me during the reading remediation, and actually this student has an intellectual disability (ID). He really can only retain information for a shorter time, but there was an instance where I asked him to do a task and was able to execute it. That was the time that I realized that although he cannot read everything that a student at his level can read, he was able to successfully comprehend the most basic words, so that's how I felt that I was successful during that time.” (IDI-02)

(I had a student who was very close to me during the reading remediation, and this student actually has an intellectual disability (ID). He can only retain information for a short time, but there was a moment when I asked him to complete a task, and he was able to do it. That was when I realized that, although he cannot read everything that a student at his level can, he was able to successfully understand the most basic words. In that moment, I felt like I had achieved success.)

Additionally, Simple (pseudonym) expressed her joy at witnessing the progress of her non-reading students. She explained that by taking a gradual and patient approach, and teaching the students slowly and carefully, she was able to help them improve their reading skills. Seeing her students develop their reading abilities over time brought her a deep sense of fulfillment and satisfaction. She stated that:

“Just like my student before she's a girl then at first she doesn't really know how to read di jud siya kabalo so nag focus ko sa iyaha

because we are applying one on one reading intervention so at first gi apply nko ang sounds so after almost 1 year non-reader gihapun siya kay naa pa mn mi sa sounds, the second year the following year nag blend name ug sound medyo happy nko kay at least maka blend na siya ug sound so the following year naga blending na gyud mi then tha third while naga blend mi mu adtu name samisa ka syllable so naa nay changes from non-reader to struggling reader.” (IDI-03)

(Just like my student before she is a girl, at first she does not really know how to read, so I focus on that student because we are applying one-on-one reading intervention, so at first I apply sounds, so after almost a year she is still a non-reader. The following year, we already blended sound. I am a bit happy at that time because at least she can blend sounds, so the following year we are still blending, and then the third year we proceed to syllables, so there are changes from non-reader to struggling reader.)

Moreover, Approachable (pseudonym) shared that transforming a non-reader into a confident reader fills her with immense pride and satisfaction. Witnessing the progress these students make and knowing the positive impact it has on their lives brings her unparalleled joy. For her, the journey of helping a student overcome reading challenges is a deeply rewarding experience that fuels her passion. She stated that:

“There was a time last year natutukan jud nako, babae tu siya natutukan nako siya at first napansin nako nganga jud siya dle pa jud siya kabalo ug sounds kaayu ang uban sounds sa letter kay malimtan pa niya, later on kay gi tutukan man nako mga at least once a week mi magkita and willing man siya to learn how to read and pag end sa school year kay though nganga pa gihapun pero makabasa na gyud siya non-reader.” (IDI-04)

(There was a time last year I focused on that one student, she is a girl. At first, I noticed that she really did not know the sounds of the letters, but because I focused on her at least once a week, we saw each other, and I noticed that she had a willingness to learn how to read, and at the end of the school year, though she could not utter the words properly, she could already read, she is not a non-reader anymore.)

Lastly, Enthusiastic (pseudonym) expressed pride in her role as a reading coordinator because she has made a significant impact on her students' lives. She feels accomplished for successfully helping non-readers become readers. Seeing her students improve and gain confidence in their reading skills brings her a great sense of satisfaction and achievement. She stated that:

“I’m so proud of myself, out of 24 isa ra jud ang di na kabasa. I’m so proud of myself nga I contributed a lot sa ilahang future sa mga kadtu na mga bata I was wondering before kung kaya kaha ni pero grabe gyud na kaya ra gyud ang all.” (IDI-05)

(I am so proud of myself, out of 24 non-readers, there is only one student who remains a non-reader. I am so proud of myself because I contributed a lot to their future. I was wondering before if I could do it, but I manage everything.)

Conclusions

To sum up, this study focuses on the scaffolding of non-reader students by high school reading coordinators. The results of this study showed that reading coordinators use a variety of strategies in order to scaffold children who are not readers. They use guided individual reading, interactive learning activities, a good classroom environment, and peer tutoring as a scaffolding technique for students who are not readers. They also go back to the fundamentals of reading instruction. Thus, the researcher came to the conclusion that there are ways to assist non-readers, even though reading coordinators deal with students' short attention spans and poor retention, a lack of parental support, and students who felt embarrassed about learning to read.

However, despite their experiences, they overcome those because they developed coping mechanisms to help them manage their responsibilities. Prioritizing reading remediation, considering into account the situation and background of the student, utilizing reward systems, and having a solid commitment to learning are a few examples of these coping strategies. Many of the teachers never stopped reminding themselves of their objectives and motivations for continuing to scaffold students who are not readers. Thus, the study came to the conclusion that reading coordinators' lives are in fact manageable based on the difficulties they encounter. Many reading coordinators are able to successfully balance their academic endeavors with their obligations, despite the fact that it takes a great deal of work and sacrifice. The research indicates that this is feasible with the correct support and resources in place. Reading coordinators also wish to emphasize the importance of students' foundations, increase reading instruction, and value each student's individuality. In order to effectively manage non-reader pupils, reading coordinators believe that they must exhibit unflinching patience. Ultimately, the accomplishments and advancements of the students will bring them a sense of fulfillment.

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